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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Abbreviation	Meaning
AC	Associated Countries
CoP	Community of Practice
EC	European Commission
EGET	European Gender Equality Taskforce
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equality
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GE	Gender equality
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GBV	Gender-based violence
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEA	Higher Education Authority
HEI	Higher Education Institution
KIF	Committee for Gender Balance and Diversity in Research
MS	EU Member States
NCP	National Contact Point
NPI	National Impact Plan
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RHEI	Research and Higher Education Institution
R&I	Research & Innovation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
SWG GRI	Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation
WEF	World Economic Forum
WP	Work Package

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This benchmark report presents an analysis of the Gender Equality Plan (GEP) requirement at the national/regional level in research and innovation (R&I) or higher education, mandated by law or/and policy in the European Research Area (ERA). It is developed within the ongoing GENDERACTIONplus project, which contributes to the coordination of the gender equality and inclusiveness objectives of the new ERA.

The main objectives of the report are to:

- present the results of the benchmarking survey and create a baseline understanding of current GEP requirements at national/regional level in R&I
- provide an overview of the overall policy framework on GEP requirement concerning ERA stakeholders
- provide an overview of relevant policy developments on the GEP requirement in ERA, mainly targeting national authorities.

Benchmark survey data on the GEP requirement was collected from responses by the GENDERACTIONplus partners (comprised of 15 countries/regions and 19 Research Funding Organisations – RFO), however RFOs are not included in this analysis. A detailed analysis of the current overall policy framework on the GEP requirement in ERA identifies relevant gaps and points to strategies for future policy development. The key findings are as follows:

- GEPs are mandatory in the majority of the surveyed countries/regions and the Plans apply predominantly to public sector entities. GEP national requirements (or the lack thereof) highlight the ongoing divide between the Member States (MS) that joined the EU before and after 2004. For post 2004 Member States, RFOs can significantly contribute to creating favourable framework conditions for GEP development.
- Intersectionality is an underdeveloped area as regards GEP requirements. There is evidence of challenges in relation to the inclusion of dimensions other than gender in GEP development and elaboration of effective measures against inequalities running along different axes. These can be attributed to a lack of in-depth knowledge about intersectionality coupled with the difficulty in understanding the term and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) restrictions.
- The Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion exerted noticeable impact on the national gender equality activities in R&I, which is demonstrated particularly by the increase in approved GEPs in R&I institutions, the organisation of workshops and trainings on GEPs, dedication of resources for gender equality work and an increase in requests addressed to the National Contact Points (NCP; e.g., queries in relation to GEP elaboration or EC requirements).
- National monitoring and evaluation systems for GEPs are a key challenge that is augmented by the increasing number of GEPs in higher education and R&I institutions. The data collected through the monitoring systems greatly varies between the countries together with their approach to publicly available GEPs database and elaboration of monitoring indicators. National evaluation systems for GEPs implementation are not widespread, yet are considered to be established in the number of surveyed countries.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. About the project

Building on the Horizon 2020 project GENDERACTION, the overall goal of GENDERACTIONplus is to contribute to the coordination of the gender equality and inclusiveness objectives of the new European Research Area through the development of two communities of practice (CoPs), one consisting of representatives of national authorities and the second consisting of representatives of RFOs. The network is made up of a total of 22 Member States (MS) and 3 Associated Countries (AC), as well as 26 project partners and 14 associated partners.

Adding the plus sign to the title of the previous GENDERACTION project not only indicates that it is a follow-up project but also makes it explicit that this project also addresses diversity and intersectionality (the gender+ approach).

Specifically, the GENDERACTIONplus project aims to:

- develop strategic policy advice on existing and emerging policy solutions
- enhance the policy-making process by engaging with stakeholders, civil society organisations, and citizens
- build capacities, competence, and expertise for gender equality and mainstreaming in R&I among the policy and RFO community members, with special attention to countries with a less comprehensive policy
- create an impact through communication, dissemination, and exploitation.

Thematically, the project focuses on:

- intersectionality and inclusiveness
- gender-based violence (GBV)
- gender dimension in research and innovation
- monitoring and evaluating gender equality actions in ERA
- promoting institutional change through GEPs.

GENDERACTIONplus aims to achieve the following impacts:

- Advance policy coordination among MS and AC countries and through stakeholder and citizen engagement.
- Improve research careers and working conditions in European R&I, by developing policy dialogue and solutions on inclusion and intersectionality, combating gender-based violence, and promoting institutional changes through GEPs.
- Improve research quality and the social responsibility of knowledge by integrating the gender dimension into R&I.
- Reduce geographic inequality by targeting less experienced/engaged countries and regions.

1.2. Objectives of the report

The main objectives of the report are to:

- present the results of the benchmarking survey and create a baseline understanding of current GEP requirements at national/regional level in R&I
- provide an overview of the overall policy framework on GEP requirement concerning ERA stakeholders
- provide an overview of relevant policy developments on the GEP requirement in ERA, mainly targeting national authorities.

This part of the GENDERACTIONplus benchmark is important in understanding the current landscape for GEPs in R&I, particularly in the context of the recent introduction of the GEP requirement for Horizon Europe. The benchmark will feed into the upcoming tasks in GENDERACTIONplus and the development of the monitoring and evaluation mechanisms. It will also facilitate an initial assessment of the impact of the GEP requirement for Horizon Europe.

1.3. The relationship of this report to other tasks and work packages

This report links to Work Package (WP) 2 on Intersectionality and inclusiveness as part of the GENDERACTIONplus project approach to mainstream intersectionality and inclusiveness into WPs 3-6. At the EU level it is expected that an intersectional perspective will be factored into the design and implementation of inclusive GEPs. The focus on the GEP requirement links to Work Package 4 in relation to GEP requirements on the gender dimension in R&I. It also feeds into Work Package 5 on monitoring and evaluation of ERA gender equality policies, however, WP5 focuses on the EU level monitoring actions for the ERA. The results of this report also link to Work Package 7 on capacity building, through the identification of needs in relation to GEP requirements, monitoring and evaluation and feeding into the design of the capacity building actions for the Policy and RFO CoPs. Additionally, this report links to Work Package 8, specifically feeding into the policy transfer and stakeholder and citizen engagement through the identification of needs and emerging practices related to GEPs and especially through engaging relevant stakeholders on the monitoring and evaluation methodology to be developed in this WP 6.

The findings of this report will feed into the remaining tasks in Work Packages 6 and the related deliverables: D6.2 Guidance for establishment of GEP monitoring systems and D6.3 Evaluation system for GEP impact.

2. POLICY BACKGROUND

Gender equality and gender mainstreaming have been ERA priorities since 2012 (EC 2013), with three specific objectives for gender equality:

- achieving a gender balance in research teams
- achieving a gender balance in decision making
- strengthening the gender dimension in research.

GEPs have emerged as the dominant policy instrument for advancing gender equality in R&I institutions. The 2015 Council conclusions *Advancing gender equality in the European Research Area* (Council of the EU 2015) encouraged MS to incorporate institutional change into their national policy framework on gender equality in R&I and encouraged MS to provide incentives to institutions to implement or further develop GEPs.

The Council conclusions on the new ERA of 1 December 2020 (Council of the EU 2020) called on the EC and MS for ‘a renewed focus on gender equality and mainstreaming, including through the instrument of gender equality plans and the integration of the gender dimension into R&I content.’ It also invited MS and RFOs ‘to advance measures to ensure that allocation of research funding is not affected by gender bias.’

While the previous conclusions and priority areas did not make GEPs mandatory, in 2020, *A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025* stated: ‘in the field of research and innovation, the Commission will introduce new measures to strengthen gender equality in Horizon Europe, such as the possibility to require a gender equality plan from applicants and an initiative to increase the number of women-led technology start-ups. Funding for gender and intersectional research will also be made available’ (EC 2020b).

Subsequently, the *General annexes* to the Horizon Europe 2021-2022 Work Programme (EC 2022b) introduced the requirement that all legal entities from MS and AC (that are public bodies, research organisations or higher education institutions, HEIs) must have a GEP to be eligible to participate in Horizon Europe for calls with deadlines in 2022 and onwards. The GEP must cover the following minimum process-related requirements:

1. Be a public document: The GEP must be a formal document signed by the top management and disseminated within the institution. It should demonstrate a commitment to gender equality, set clear goals and detailed actions and measures to achieve them.
2. Have dedicated resources: Resources for the design, implementation, and monitoring of GEPs may include funding for specific positions such as equality officers or gender equality teams as well as earmarked working time for academic, management and administrative staff.
3. Include arrangements for data collection and monitoring: GEPs must be evidence-based and founded on sex or gender-disaggregated baseline data collected across all staff categories. This data should inform the GEP’s objectives and targets, indicators, and ongoing evaluation of progress, and be reported on annually.
4. Be supported by training and capacity-building: Actions should address gender equality and unconscious gender biases and may include developing gender competence establishing

working groups dedicated to specific topics, and raising awareness through workshops and communication activities.

In addition to the four mandatory process-related requirements, the following five thematic areas are recommended for content:

- work-life balance and organisational culture
- gender balance in leadership and decision-making
- gender equality in recruitment and career progression
- integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
- measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment.

In 2021, the Standing Working Group on Gender in Research and Innovation (SWG GRI) highlighted that the absence of a GEP requirement in a country is not an indicator of quality or absence of activity, noting that there are many bottom-up activities and policy alignments taking place in MS that serve to advance gender equality (SWG GRI 2021, p. 4). The survey showed that in relation to supporting GEP implementation at the European level:

- countries with and without a GEP requirement show the same interest in mutual learning on GEPs and exchange of knowledge at the institutional level about GEPs (76%)
- 59% of MS and AC showed an interest in opportunities to research the impact of GEPs in the ERA.

Now that GEPs have become a widespread tool to advance gender equality across European Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), there is a need to map how MS and AC are monitoring their implementation and how they support GEP development and implementation at national level.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Target groups

The benchmarking survey targeted national authorities (ministries, national agencies and organisations that support them) and RFOs. Overall, 113 representatives of national authorities, supporting organisations and RFOs within and outside the consortium were addressed with a request to (help to) ensure the answers to the questionnaires.

3.2. Data collection

The benchmarking survey was disseminated on 10 October 2022 with the deadline on 6 November 2022. In the case of some respondents, there was an agreement to postpone the deadline (often because of the need to coordinate the collection of information for the questionnaire across the organisation and/or because of the heavy workload in the autumn and as the end of the year approaches). The last inputs were received on 18 November 2022.

3.3. Mapping instruments

The data were gathered through the LimeSurvey platform. To facilitate the work of coordinating inputs, a Word version of the questionnaires was sent to respondents along with a link to the questionnaire in the outreach email. Most of the inputs were entered via online questionnaire, in two cases (Slovakia, Belgium) the answers were sent in a word document.

3.4. Data clearing

For the overall benchmark survey, all data with survey answers was downloaded from LimeSurvey as Excel files. Attached documents were mostly in PDF format (only exceptionally in Word files).

In the Excel files with answers partial adjustments have been made to the few initial questions in respondents' inputs, e.g., change or adding of country name to country code (Poland => PL, Spain => ES), in one case the name of organisation was omitted by the respondent and was therefore added in the data cleaning phase. The two answers to the survey submitted in Word file were manually added to the Excel files. In the next step, the answers that were complete were filtered. The duplicate inputs have been omitted.

The survey questions for the mapping in WP6 included specific questions on intersectionality and inclusion as an effort to identify the current status of these policies among the consortium members and to ensure this topic is mainstreamed into all thematic WPs.

For the WP6 questions, there were sixteen responses from national authorities (including 2 from Belgium). Data was analysed quantitatively and qualitatively through data integration, clustering of the respondent countries and analysis of the accompanying additional documents provided by the national experts. Comparing the respondent countries was challenging as the level of detail provided in responses to the benchmark survey varied, as was the case with the accompanying documents which included varying levels of granularity.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1. Gender Equality Plan requirement at the national/regional level in research and innovation or higher education, mandated by law or/and policy

A general requirement to have gender equality plans at the national or regional level is in place in half of the sixteen countries/regions whose representatives contributed to the benchmarking study. These are **Austria, Croatia, Greece, Ireland, Norway, Spain, Sweden and the Flemish Region of Belgium**¹. Furthermore, in the **Czech Republic** and **Denmark**, which have no law or policy resulting

¹ According to the report of the SWG GRI (2021), requirements for GEPs are also in place in **Finland, France, Germany, Iceland, and Switzerland**. Representatives of these countries did not participate in the benchmarking

from a government decision, other mechanisms that actually 'prompt' or even 'push' institutions to implement the GEP, are in place (see section 4.1.1 below). In general, therefore, in ten out of sixteen countries, entities from the higher education and R&I sector are obliged in some way to have an equality plan. Currently, GEPs are not mandatory at national or regional level in **Israel, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia and the Walloon Region of Belgium**. It is worth noting the discrepancies between regions in Belgium – GEPs are required in Flanders, while in Wallonia such a condition does not have to be fulfilled.

Figure 1: GEP requirement at the national/regional level

Note: data for Bosnia and Herzegovina, Cyprus, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Iceland, Italy, Malta, the Netherlands, Slovenia, Switzerland and Turkey are drawn from the report *Gender Equality Plans as a catalyst for change* (SWG GRI 2021): answers 'Yes (data for 2021)' and 'No (data for 2021)'.

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey + SWG GRI.

study that is the subject of this report; however, under the assumption of no significant changes during the relatively short gap between the two studies (2021 versus 2022), we decided to include the missing cases in Figure 1.

When looking at the GEP requirements from a geographical perspective, two patterns are noticeable. Firstly, the countries surveyed that joined the European Union in 2004 or later are less likely to have GEP requirements or may not have data for 2021. Secondly, mandatory GEPs are favoured by the Nordic countries, which are renowned for implementing comprehensive gender equality policies in various sectors and areas of life. What is more, they are consistently ranked among the highest in the world on measures of gender equality, such as the Gender Equality Index (EIGE 2022) and the Global Gender Gap Index (WEF 2022). Of the countries surveyed who joined the EU after 2004, this requirement is only in place in **Croatia** (with additional mechanisms also in the **Czech Republic**).

4.1.1. Countries with other mechanisms in place

As mentioned above, the **Czech Republic** and **Denmark** are countries without GEP requirements in higher education and R&I sector that results from a government decision, but with other strong mechanisms. In case of the Czech Republic, research funding organisations play a key role in the process of creating favourable environment for GEPs. The Czech Science Foundation (Grantová agentura České republiky, GAČR), the main organisation that provides funding for basic research, adopted a GEP requirement in some of its programmes, and the same is envisaged for the Technology Agency (Technologická agentura České republiky, TACR), which is responsible for grants on applied research. As these two independent public organisations cover the lion's share of grants for research, they have an impact on most higher education and research and innovation institutions, whose scientific staff are dependent on project funding.

Denmark does not have provisions which refer specifically to HEI and R&I sector, however all public institutions with fifty or more employees have an obligation to report on gender equality, according to the Act on Gender Equality. These institutions shall provide data and other information at least once every two years: (1) whether the ministry, the institution or the company has formulated an equality policy and, if applicable, the detailed content of this; (2) the gender distribution in relation to the individual job categories and (3) other conditions that are deemed to be important for the assessment of the organisation's efforts in the field of equality. In the process of analysing benchmark replies that involved bilateral contacts with the respondents, Danish respondents note that there is a focus on balanced representation in leadership and concrete objectives for improvement actions, but an interpretation as to which tiers of management this applies to is rather open.

4.1.2. Organisations to which the GEP requirement applies to

The widest range of organisations covered by the GEP requirement in the higher education and R&I sectors can be found in Sweden where equality plans shall be implemented in all public and private entities. In **Croatia** and **Norway**, the GEP requirement applies to all organisations except for private R&I companies (Croatia), and private RPOs (Norway). It is far more common for the requirement to be directed at public sector entities; the requirement in **Greece** and **Belgium-Flanders** does not apply to

private bodies², in **Austria**, apart from public HEIs and public RPOs, GEP is mandatory only for private HEIs so private RPOs as well as R&I companies are not covered by GEP requirement. In all cases except **Belgium-Flanders** the GEP requirement applies to public higher education institutions. Similarly, in all cases except Ireland, the GEP requirement applies to public research performing organisations. In the **Belgium-Flanders** the obligation concerns only public RPOs,³ and in **Ireland** only public HEIs (it is striking particularly in the case of Ireland, that implements a wide array of mechanisms regarding gender equality, but all of them are targeted to public higher education institutions⁴). In addition, **Spain** expands this requirement to research funding organisations and foundations for R&I that are considered public agents of the R&I system.

Table 1: Countries with GEP requirement and organisations to which the GEP requirement applies to

Respondent country	Public sector			Private sector			Total
	HEIs	RPOs	Administrative bodies	HEIs	RPOs	R&I companies	
AT	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	3
BE-FL	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	1
EL	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	3
ES	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	4
HR	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	5
IE	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	1
NO	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	5
SE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	6
Total	7	7	5	4	2	3	

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

² In Greece, according to the National Action Plan for Gender Equality 2021-2025 (<https://isotita.gr/wp-content/uploads/2021/12/%CE%95%CE%A3%CE%94%CE%99%CE%A6-2021-2025.pdf>, retrieved 26 June 2023), private sector entities are encouraged to adopt gender equality plans.

³ However GEPs are a required for Flemish HEIs to receive funding from their main governmental research fund (GENDER-NET 2015, p. 10).

⁴ For context, Ireland does not have a high number of public RPOs or private HEIs, and these do not fall under the remit of the Higher Education Authority (HEA) which operates under a specific legislative context whereby it works with publicly funded HEIs. The HEA has a statutory responsibility, at central government level, for the effective governance and regulation of higher education institutions and the higher education system.

In some countries there are different obligations which depend on the number of employees. In **Norway** the Equality and Anti-discrimination Act imposes the obligation of making active, targeted and systematic efforts to ensure gender equality in all public and private organisations with more than fifty employees⁵. In **Spain** the Organic Law on Effective Equality between Women and Men from 2007 states that institutions and companies with 50 or more employees are obliged to prepare and implement equality plans, following negotiation or consultation with female and male workers. The threshold of 50 employees applies also to **Denmark**, which does not have a special requirement for higher education and R&I institutions. In **Croatia** legal entities with more than 20 employees, are required to have anti-discrimination provisions and measures with a view to achieving gender equality in their general acts.

In **Sweden**, the range of active measures which are required to be documented by all workplaces depend on the number of employees and is as follows:

- 25 employees and more: all elements of their work on active measures shall be documented
- 10–24 employees: work on pay surveys shall be documented
- 9 employees and fewer: active measures shall be taken, but a documentation is not required.

4.2. Intersections of GEP requirement with other discriminatory grounds

Among the countries with a GEP requirement in the higher education and R&I sector, **Croatia, Greece, Ireland** and **Norway** include the intersection of different grounds of discrimination, in addition to gender. Ethnicity is the most common factor (marked by all four countries), followed by age and gender identity (marked by three countries, except Ireland).⁶ In Greece, the GEP requirement covers the widest array of intersectional factors. The question of intersectionality is included in a more broadly conceived policy, which recognises the need to include both gender identity and sexual orientation in measures to combat discrimination, encouraging the holistic treatment of inequalities that run along axes such as gender, identity and sexuality. Norway also stands out positively – only the socio-economic background is not included, but another potential factor of unequal treatment, namely care responsibilities, is addressed. In Ireland the question of ethnicity is a part of the Athena Swan framework – since the charter was redeveloped in 2021 HEIs shall submit intersectional analyses with consideration of ethnicity and have the option to include data on additional equality grounds. It resulted from the fact that the different stakeholders noted the need for moving beyond a binary men versus women approach to data collection, for instance a lack of gender equality data disaggregated by ethnicity makes it impossible to determine 'which women are progressing' (HEA 2022, p. 22).

⁵ However, smaller organisations also have specific reporting obligations (see more in the section 'Emerging practices regarding GEP legal provisions in national frameworks and national GEP monitoring systems').

⁶ In Ireland, the [Athena Swan Charter Principles](#) (revised in 2021) include that HEIs will commit to 'fostering collective understanding that individuals have the right to determine and affirm their gender, and to implementing inclusive and effective policies and practices that are cognisant of the lived experiences and needs of trans and non-binary people'.

Figure 2: Intersectional categories included in GEP requirements

Note: purple – category included, red – category not included.

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

There is a noticeably limited awareness and understanding of the complex intersections between gender and other characteristics, as the European Commission report states: *Based on the review of emerging activity, a key challenge for the promotion of inclusive gender equality plans and policies in European R&I will be to raise awareness and understanding of equality and diversity challenges in relation to different characteristics. A growing community of RPOs and RFOs and some national authorities clearly acknowledge the need to take broader action that builds on existing gender equality policies and actions* (EC 2022a, p. 6). A lack of systemic, disaggregated, and comparable data on diversity characteristics can be linked to the different approaches to the data protection. The EC notices that despite of differences between national legal frameworks there are no absolute prohibitions on the collection of data on race, ethnicity, sexual orientation, gender identity or disability, yet concerns about the disclosure of some types of data or its misuse by public authorities may result in difficulties in data collection (ibid., p. 39). A recommendation that any measures to collect sensitive personal data should be developed transparently and in partnership with marginalised groups, with clear links and accountability for actions, building on GDPR principles (ibid., p. 44) is crucial in this regard. This makes intersectionality both a very important and sensitive issue. Considering that experts believe there is a lack of in-depth knowledge about intersectionality and that it is a difficult issue to grasp and measure, consequently, a challenge arises in how to include other dimensions or intersections in GEPs and effective measures to address them (EC 2022a, 2022c).

4.3. Contribution of GEP requirement to the development of inclusive research careers

In a similar way to intersectionality, in four countries – **Croatia, Greece, Spain** and **Sweden** – the GEP requirement should contribute to the development of inclusive research careers. Respondents from Croatia admit that GEP places greater emphasis on the importance of equality and inclusion of women in research processes. In Greece the national action plan for gender equality refers to the need to strengthen skills and new technologies and research, especially for women, so that they have equal opportunities in competitive workplaces, in order to strengthen their position. Some ministries aim to design innovative actions that will boost the attraction of more girls to study in STEM and aim to increase the participation rate of women in businesses based on research and innovation. In Sweden targeted areas and activities proposed, as well as mandatory demands on, for instance, social security, aim directly and indirectly to support inclusive research careers. In Spain, while GEPs have always addressed direct and indirect gender discrimination in research careers, this is not specifically addressed in requirements related to GEP content. The response from Spain indicated hopes that the Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion will reinforce this trend.

4.4. Effect of Horizon Europe Gender Equality Plans eligibility criterion on national gender equality activities in research and innovation

In response to the GENDERACTIONplus benchmark survey, 16 consortium partners (beneficiaries and associate partners) assessed the extent to which the Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion exerted influence on gender equality in research and innovation in their countries.

Notwithstanding the low overall survey response rate, a substantial number of the respondents stated that the Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion has impacted national gender equality measures in R&I in their countries. A variation in responses ranging from ‘to no extent’ up to ‘to a very large extent’ were submitted in the survey. The most common response was ‘to some extent’ and ‘to a large extent’ – in both cases 6 out of 16 countries indicated the above scales as the measurement of the GEP Horizon Europe impact on gender equality in R&I. A summary of the responses can be found in the table below.

Figure 3: Measurement of the GEP Horizon Europe impact on gender equality national activity in R&I

Specifically, to what extent has the Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion had an effect on gender equality in research & innovation in your country?

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

This subsection provides insights into the concrete results the establishment of GEP requirement at the European level has had on the national R&I systems. The analysis shows that in numerous countries the existence of Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion triggered the development of concrete national activities aimed at supporting gender equality in R&I. With the exception of **Belgium-Flanders, Ireland** and **Sweden**, all of the respondent countries indicate a direct link between Horizon Europe GEP requirement and the increase in the number of GEPs approved in R&I institutions, as the table below shows.

Figure 4: Effect of Horizon Europe GEP requirement: new GEPs approved in RHEI and the respondent countries

What concrete effect the GEP requirement has had? [New GEPs have been approved in R&I institutions]

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

Clearly, the introduction of Horizon Europe eligibility requirement in the form of GEPs sparked a growing interest in instituting GEPs among R&I entities. The countries that had demanded GEPs (by law or policy) prior to its launch in the Horizon Europe context, perceive GEP eligibility criterion in Horizon Europe rather as enhancing the work with the national requirements in national equality legislation that had already taken place (**Norway**) or in compliance terms, namely if existing policies are in line with the Framework Programme stipulations (**Sweden**). The interest in developing GEPs and gender equality work as such is particularly visible in the new Member States. As the example of the **Czech Republic** shows, the work on gender equality is additionally enhanced when national RFOs conditions grant funding on the adoption of GEPs by the applicants. This has a direct impact on national RPOs as they and their researchers are dependent upon project funding.

Respondents were also asked about the effect the Horizon Europe GEP requirement has had on the support to build capacity at the national level. The respondents of the survey see a direct effect of Horizon Europe GEP requirement in terms of the skills development activities on GEPs that the Horizon Europe requirement contributed to.

Figure 5: Effect of Horizon Europe GEP requirement: workshops and trainings on GEPs at national level

What concrete effect the GEP requirement has had? [Workshops and training have been organised in the R&I field on GEPs at the national level]

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

Since GEPs are a novelty especially for the countries with no legal / policy obligation at the national level in the context of grant allocation, an intensification in the thematic trainings and workshops is a very welcome support mechanism for national experts and meets one of the main challenges identified in some of the previous analysis conducted on the GEPs as a policy instrument (SWG GRI 2021), where mobilising support and resources to build capacities at the national level was recognised as an area in need of further action. Since training and capacity building are also one of the core process-related requirements, an increase in this area as a result of the Horizon Europe GEP criterion can contribute to increasing the quality of GEP implementation as well as its reviews.

In connection with the question on workshops and trainings, GENDERACTIONplus benchmarking survey also explored whether the concrete effect of Horizon Europe GEP criteria manifested itself in the preparation of new tools and materials on developing and implementing GEPs in R&I.

Figure 6: Effect of Horizon Europe GEP requirement: new tools and materials developed on GEPs

What concrete effect the GEP requirement has had? [New tools and material developed on developing and implementing GEPs in R&I]

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

In countries such as **Austria, the Czech Republic, Greece, Norway, Poland, Portugal** and **Slovakia** the organisation of workshops and trainings on GEPs in R&I field at the national level was positively correlated also with the development of new tools and materials devoted to preparing and implementing GEPs in R&I institutions. In contrast, this is not the case in 9 other countries (**Belgium-Flanders, Belgium-Wallonia, Croatia, Denmark, Ireland, Israel, Lithuania, Spain, Sweden**).

The benchmarking survey among GENDERACTIONplus partners that are national authorities shows that the majority of the respondents (56%) see an increase in the volume of requests received by the National Contact Points. However, a high percentage of 44% of countries that participated in the survey do not discern such an effect of Horizon Europe GEP on the NCP scope of activity.

Figure 7: Effect of Horizon Europe GEP requirement: increase in questions posed to NCPs

What concrete effect the GEP requirement has had? [An increase in requests/questions received by NCPs as a result of the eligibility criterion]

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

National Contact Points are an essential element of domestic support structures regarding Horizon Europe implementation. Their advice seems to be particularly invaluable in the areas such as GEPs, which are one of the key novelties introduced by Horizon Europe. Professional delivery of the core functions of NCPs namely informing and awareness raising; assisting, advising and training as well as

signposting and cooperation (EC 2021) plays a very important role in the fulfilment by the national beneficiaries of the requirements set by Horizon Europe in relation to GEPs and it is oftentimes their support and advice including the trainings that guide the national stakeholders in the process of GEP preparation.

Apart from introducing four mandatory process-related requirements, the European Commission recommended five content-related (thematic) areas that GEPs could consider, specifically:

- work-life balance and organizational culture
- gender balance in leadership and decision making
- gender equality in recruitment and career progression
- integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
- measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment.

The GENDERACTIONplus benchmark analysis seeks to establish whether the above-mentioned GEP recommended thematic areas influenced R&I institutions by opening new lines of action in them. The table below shows that the majority of the national authorities that participated in the survey (69%) find that GEP recommended thematic areas have had limited influence over initiating actions associated with GEP content-related areas whereas 31% consider that such a connection is indeed visible.

Figure 8: Effect of Horizon Europe GEP requirement: opening new lines of action in R&I institutions

What concrete effect the GEP requirement has had? [The EC recommended thematic areas have opened new lines of action in R&I institutions]

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

Sustainable national financial resources for GEPs development form a support measure that incentivizes R&I institutions to work on their GEPs. As the GENDERACTIONplus survey interestingly reveals, the overwhelming majority of the countries that participated in the survey show no positive correlation between the GEP Horizon Europe requirement and the increased national funding for GEP development, except for one country (**Slovakia**). However, investment in gender equality in R&I by the national authorities, coupled with the investments by the institutions themselves, was considered to markedly contribute to achieving progress in successful implementation of GEPs and advancing a gender-equal culture.

As regards Slovakia the eligibility criterion stimulated the Slovak Centre of Scientific and Technical Information, the state research and innovation supporting institution, to allocate financial resources into the creation of the specialised consultancy support to Horizon Europe applicants with the elaboration and implementation of GEPs. Funding is provided by the national structural project SK4ERA implemented by the Centre.⁷ The consultancy support was established and launched in September 2021. A follow-up project proposal SK4ERA has recently been submitted and approved.

Figure 9: Effect of Horizon Europe GEP requirement: increased national funding for GEPs development

What concrete effect the GEP requirement has had? [Increased national funding for GEP development]

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

To point to key findings as visualized by the table below, for those countries whose national authorities assessed Horizon Europe GEP requirement as having influenced gender equality in R&I to a very large / large / some extent (13 out of 16 countries), the concrete effects of the EU obligation were shown mostly in the increase in new GEPs approved in R&I institutions (12/13, i.e. 92% of such countries observed this effect, the organization of workshop and training sessions in R&I on GEPs at the national level (10/13; 77%) and the increase in requests to NCPs on the topic of GEPs (8/13; 62%) as well as the development of new tools and material on developing and implementing GEPs in R&I (7/13; 54%). Limited effect has been recorded in relation to the opening of new, GEP thematically related lines of action in R&I institutions (5/13; 38%) and in the field of national funding earmarked for GEP development (only 1 country, 8%). Some of the countries belonging to this group also point to an increased awareness related to the equality issues both among the public in general (**Poland**) and specifically in the research environment (**Greece, Lithuania, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia** – particularly among managers and HR personnel). Apart from the growing interest in some countries in the creation of GEPs themselves (**Lithuania, Poland, Portugal**) some countries also mention the direct effect of Horizon Europe GEP being the creation of internal gender equality dedicated structures (**Poland, Portugal**). Interestingly, in **Austria**, Horizon Europe GEP criterion was an element conducive to discussions held between national authorities and R&I stakeholders on the National Action Plan and reflections on the past developments as well as recommendations for the future landscape of Austrian higher education and its research and innovation. For **Denmark** the scope of future audits aimed at GEPs are a point of concern in the context

⁷ https://www.cvtisr.sk/cvti-sr-vedecka-kniznica/projekty/narodne-projekty/sk4era-internacionalizacia-sk-vyskumu.html?page_id=23804 (retrieved 26 June 2023).

of fulfilling the eligibility criterion regarding participation in a Horizon Europe project and insecurity that is connected with an organization's admissibility, which Denmark points out when describing effect of Horizon Europe GEP on national R&I activities.

Figure 10: Effect of Horizon Europe GEP requirement: summary (countries indicating very large/large/some extent of HE GEP influence)

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

In contrast, in countries where the effect of the Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion is assessed as little or none, which is the case in 3 out of 16 countries (**Ireland, Israel and Sweden**), certain implications of the GEP eligibility criterion have nonetheless been identified: in Israel, new GEPs have been approved in R&I institutions and workshops and trainings have been organised and in Sweden, the number of questions received by NCP has increased. Additionally, Ireland indicated that there is greater awareness and support for the need for GEPs among research-focused staff who would have been previously unaware of this or disengaged with GEPs.

4.5. GEP building blocks: comparison between Horizon Europe and national requirements

As indicated above, in reply to the question on the mandatory GEPs required at the national/regional level in higher education or research and innovation, 8 countries indicated the presence of such an obligation. The survey further explored the link between the mandatory requirements existing at the EU and national levels by asking which of the HE building blocks are also required at the national level.

According to the survey, 5 out of 8 countries (**Ireland, Greece, Norway, Spain, and Sweden**) that require GEPs at the national level, indicated that the national requirement complies with the building blocks set at the EU level, to a varying degree, however. In turn, 3 countries (**Austria, Croatia, and Belgium-Flanders**) indicated that there is no correspondence between GEP requirement at the national level and Horizon Europe GEP mandatory building blocks.

Table 2: Horizon Europe GEP building blocks and their reflection in national GEP requirements

Countries with national GEP requirement	Compliance (Yes) or lack thereof (No) between national and European GEP building blocks
AT	No
BE-FL	No
EL	Yes
ES	Yes
HR	No
IE	Yes
NO	Yes
SE	Yes

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

Two out of five countries that responded positively to the question on national GEP requirement show the maximum degree of alignment between the EU and national obligations (**Sweden and Ireland**). In those countries all of the above-mentioned GEP building blocks established in the context of Horizon Europe eligibility criterion are also reflected in the national requirements. In the case of Ireland, the building blocks were included as a national requirement in the *Second HEA National Review of Gender Equality in Irish Higher Education Institutions* (HEA 2022). The expert group that prepared the document

issued the following key recommendations regarding the national requirements on the institutional GEPs:

At a minimum all Irish Higher Education Institutions should:

- have an institutional Gender Equality Action Plan that is published on the HEI website, signed by the President, actively communicated and progress monitored within the institution
- demonstrate a commitment to provide sufficient resources and expertise in gender equality, particularly in relation to the implementation of its institutional Gender Equality Action Plan
- have a vice-president (or equivalent) with responsibility for equality, diversity and inclusion who is a member of the HEI executive/management team
- collect and analyse sex/gender-disaggregated data on staff to inform the institutional strategy for advancement of gender equality
- provide training towards sustaining the advancement of gender equality for all staff.

Evidence that these requirements have been met should be provided to the HEA through annual reporting (HEA 2022, p. 9).

In the case of **Sweden** it was pointed out that several RPOs and RFOs are slightly adjusting and revising their existing plans for gender mainstreaming according to the Horizon Europe GEP requirements, not because these aspects are not already in place but rather because the GEP requirement is systemized in a slightly different way than existing action plans for gender mainstreaming in most RPOs and RFOs.

Slightly lower, albeit still a high level of alignment between national GEP requirements and Horizon Europe GEP building blocks is seen in the remaining three countries (**Greece, Norway, and Spain**). All three countries lack the commitment of dedicated resources at the national level. Additionally, **Norway** and **Spain** do not require the awareness raising/training activities on gender equality and unconscious gender biases for staff and decision-makers.

Table 3: Horizon Europe GEP building blocks and their fulfilment in national GEP requirements

Respondent country	Horizon Europe GEP mandatory building blocks			
	Publication	Dedicated resources	Data collection and monitoring	Training
EL	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
ES	Yes	No	Yes	No
IE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
NO	Yes	No	Yes	No
SE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

4.6. Impact of GEPs on gender equality

Representatives from 11 countries responded to the question ‘What impact on gender equality in your country have specific features of GEPs had’. The following features of the plans were identified in the question, with answers ranked from 1 (no impact) to 5 (strong impact). Across the countries/regions participating in the survey, the following GEP features were ranked highest on the 1-5 scale:

- dedicated resources for gender equality work (8): **Croatia, the Czech Republic, Greece, Ireland, Norway, Poland, Portugal, and Sweden**
- integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content (3): **Croatia, Greece, and Sweden**
- measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment (5): **Croatia, Greece, Poland, Portugal, and Spain**
- monitoring of gender equality in recruitment and promotion processes at the institutional level (7): **Austria, Croatia, Greece, Ireland, Norway, Poland, and Portugal**
- public availability of GEPs (6): **Austria, Croatia, Greece, Norway, Portugal, and Sweden**
- reporting on gender balance in leadership and decision-making (6): **Croatia, Greece, Ireland, Norway, Portugal, and Sweden**
- system for collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data (5): **Croatia, Greece, Norway, Portugal, and Sweden**
- training and capacity building plans (7): **Croatia, Greece, Ireland, Norway, Poland, Portugal, and Sweden.**

The impact of the GEP is slightly above average, with dedicated resources having the strongest impact (a concrete action that can change the *status quo*) and integration of the gender dimension having the weakest impact (according to the authors of this report, this measure might be difficult to capture in the GEP). Some interesting differences between countries are noticeable, for example, in the **Czech**

Republic reports on gender balance in leadership and decision-making in GEPs were not highlighted as impacting on gender equality. In the **Czech Republic** and **Ireland**, the integration of the gender dimension in research and teaching content into GEPs was not highlighted as impacting on gender equality. In **Denmark**, measures against gender-based violence were not ranked highly (and other factors do not exceed 4). In **Spain**, GBV is the paramount issue whereas dedicated resources and integration of the gender dimension are of some importance, and other factors were not ranked highly. In **Sweden**, the issue of GBV was given a low ranking, perhaps because it is addressed very broadly, at different levels and in different areas, and its inclusion in the GEP is secondary to other measures.

For some countries, it is worth noting which factors are the most important (in the situation where one or two were marked as 5 or 4). For **Austria** crucial factors are public availability of GEPs and monitoring of gender equality in recruitment and promotion. The **Czech Republic** emphasizes the importance of dedicated resources for gender equality work, as does **Ireland**, for which also reporting on gender balance in decision-making plays a role. In **Norway**, the system for collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data is of key importance. Norwegian respondents give the highest priority also to the additional factor, not mentioned in the questionnaire – the legal GEP requirement at the national and European (Horizon Europe) levels. Finally, **Spain** highlighted the measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment as a main feature of GEPs that contributes to the overall gender equality in higher education and R&I system.

Figure 11: Features of GEPs which have impact on gender equality

Note: the graph presents responses to the questions on the 5-point Likert scale (1 = no impact, 5 = strong impact). Positive (4, 5 points) and negative options (1, 2 points) head on different directions with neutral option (3) at the centre. Percentages at both ends denote summarized positive or negative answers. Percentages in the middle refer to the neutral opinion.

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

Respondents from **Israel, Lithuania, and the Walloon region of Belgium** noted that it is too early to assess impact of very recently adopted GEPs. Others note that even if the measures are in place, sometimes they do not work perfectly. For example, in Norway resources for gender equality work are allocated, but surveys at HEIs reveal decreasing amount of them over the last few years. This can have a negative impact on gender equality work. This points to the fact that the perception of effectiveness of measures may be context/country specific.

5. NATIONAL MONITORING AND EVALUATION SYSTEMS FOR GEP IMPLEMENTATION

5.1. National monitoring systems for GEP implementation

This part of the benchmark analysis explores the subject of GEP-related monitoring systems. More precisely, it provides insights into the presence / absence of such a system in the national frameworks where the respondents indicated that a monitoring system regarding GEPs is in place (the benchmark question specifically asked whether a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring). It also provides analysis of the accompanying features that refer to data collection including the category of the data collected, institutions obliged to report, periodicity of reporting and the way the collected data is used by the responsible authority. In the ensuing part of the analysis insights are provided with reference to indicators, possible connection with the ERA monitoring system, publicly available database of GEPs and measurement of impact in terms of defined gender equality priorities. Finally, exploration of the link between the Horizon Europe-related GEP features and scope of national monitoring systems is being conducted.

Monitoring of GEP implementation has a potential to influence the quality of gender equality discourse in Member States and Associated Countries as well as draw conclusions across Europe as regards transformative potential of GEPs in terms of changing institutional culture. In order for it to happen, sound monitoring frameworks, including elaboration of indicators, need to be in place. As indicated in the monitoring session of the event organised by the European Commission to discuss key findings of Ecorys study on the GEPs impact (Wroblewski & Müller 2023) data collected through monitoring should indeed be used to discuss developments in GEPs implementation including barriers in implementing certain actions. Linked to that, monitoring of GEPs remains a challenge in the sense of capturing impact stemming from the implemented actions planned and implemented through institutional GEPs.

5.1.1. Existence of GEP monitoring system

Out of 16 countries participating in the survey, 8 require GEPs at national level. 6 of these 8 indicate the presence of a national / regional system for GEP monitoring (**Croatia, Greece, Ireland, Norway, Spain, and Sweden**) while 10 do not have GEP monitoring systems in place.

5.1.2. Institutions gathering data

As far as the institutions that gather data on GEPs are concerned, these are mostly ministries / ministerial specialised units (**Croatia, Norway, and Spain**) or agencies directly linked to the ministries (**Ireland** – Higher Education Authority, **Sweden** – Swedish Agency for Gender Equality). **Greece**

indicated that monitoring for the evaluation and implementation of existing equality policies is done at an institutional level within the framework of the National Council for Gender Equality. In order to strengthen the consultation and further encourage the dialogue of the involved bodies, the expansion of its members has already been institutionalized by law.

5.1.3. Type of data collected

The data that is collected refers to a wide range of gender equality-related outputs and measures, depending on the national system. The analysis shows that through the monitoring systems, the national authorities gather information on both qualitative and quantitative data and the scope of the data collected varies, with countries taking different approaches to the required data. This variety also contributes to actual barriers in ensuring sound comparisons between the countries. The summary of the data collected through the national/regional system for national GEP monitoring can be found below.

Table 4: Data collected through national monitoring systems

Respondent country	Data collected
ES	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GE structures • GEPs fields of action such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ training ○ sexual harassment protocols ○ work-life balance measures ○ communication and sensitization-oriented measures ○ selection procedures and career progression ○ gender balance in decision-making
IE	Confirmation of Athena Swan Award status and associated GEP
NO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The current state of gender equality in the institution (i.e. pay gap, part-time employment, distribution) of different position levels • Equality measures undertaken to promote or planned to promote the purpose of Norwegian Equality and Anti-discrimination Act referring to the equality
SE	GEP aims, goals, activities, organization, budget

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

Croatia stated that it collects data on female/male researchers and female/male project coordinators which is related to a general monitoring on gender equality in R&I rather than specifically to GEPs. For this reason, Croatia was not included in the table above.

When it comes to the duty to fulfill the monitoring requirements, it predominantly refers to the public institutions. In **Norway**, among the institutions that are obliged to report on their GEPs there are additionally private undertakings with more than 50 employees. The obligations set by the national authorities with reference to the type of institutions required to provide data are set out in the table below.

Table 5: Institutions obliged to report on gender equality

Respondent country	Institutions obliged to report
ES	Public and private universities and all public research organisations
HR	Universities and public institutions
IE	Public HEIs
NO	All public employers, regardless of size, and private employers with more than 50 employees
SE	All 38 state-funded HEIs targeted by the government assignment on gender mainstreaming

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

5.1.4. Periodicity of data collection

With reference to the periodicity of data collection, it is mostly done on an annual basis, with the exception of **Sweden** where the frequency of data collection varies but is usually every two years.

5.1.5. Use of data by national authorities

Monitoring of GEP implementation, following the logic of the complete policy cycle (Wroblewski 2020, p. 16) is one of the key factors for their successful implementation, allowing for adjustments or pointing to the areas where further action is needed to achieve the desired outcomes. Apart from the invaluable input for the institutions themselves, monitoring of GEPs can provide important feedback for the national authorities which can then use the data to inform the gender equality in R&I policy cycle process. GENDERACTIONplus benchmark survey asked about the ways the collected data on GEPs is used by the national authorities. The prevailing response refers to the reports that are prepared on the basis on the data gathered through the monitoring process (**Croatia, Ireland, and Sweden**); data is also used to inform policy decisions (**Ireland**).

In **Norway** the GEP monitoring system is an element in the process of preparation of the state budget. More specifically, the Norwegian state budget has a chapter where data on gender equality in academia is presented. There is data on female PhD students, female professors, men and women in fulltime and part-time positions. There is also data on what country background faculty at different universities have.

The national budget gives an indication of government priorities that impact university policies. Against the backdrop of equality/diversity provisions in the national budget, specifically in chapters devoted to higher education / research and innovation, the allocation letters to all RPOs in Norway are formulated and they follow the presentation of the state budget in the legislative assembly. One of the ‘steering parameters’ in the allocation letters is the number/percentage of female professors. Each year the allocation letter also includes a text on equality and diversity with emphasis being put on given aspects (for example action plans, sexual harassment or resources devoted to equality work). Each university has a multiannual performance agreement, and in annual dialogue meetings with the Ministry HEIs discuss performance based on a set of indicators (so called ‘styringsparametre’ – steering parameters).

5.1.6. Indicators

The analysis of the national GEP monitoring frameworks carried out within the GENDERACTIONplus project tried to establish whether indicators have been instituted by the national authorities to monitor GEP implementation. Half of the countries that have national/regional GEP monitoring system note that indicators have been developed (3/6), with only one country providing further details (**Ireland**). Thus, in **Croatia, Norway, Sweden, and Spain** the national GEP monitoring system is not linked to any indicators set by the national authorities.

In the case of **Ireland**, Horizon Europe GEP-related indicators are closely intertwined with the Athena Swan Ireland Charter requirements.

The Athena Swan Ireland Charter requires HEIs to have a SMART GEP meaning actions should be specific, measurable, achievable, relevant and time bound. HEIs provide rationale for the actions in their GEP, based on the findings of a critical self-assessment report. The self-assessment report outlines the baseline data and evidence of gender inequality under specific headings and is peer reviewed alongside the GEP during the Athena Swan Ireland Charter assessment process.

The self-assessment form requires applicants to address the following areas:

- letter of endorsement from the head of the institution
- governance and recognition of equality, diversity and inclusion work
- description of the self-assessment process
- overview of the institution and its context
- supporting and advancing academic and research staff careers
- supporting and advancing professional, managerial and support staff careers
- evaluating culture, inclusion and belonging
- institutional priorities for future action.

Meeting the assessment criteria for an Athena Swan award indicates that all requirements have been met, a GEP is in place and has been reviewed independently. As part of the national monitoring system, Advance HE (who runs the Athena Swan process in Ireland) notify the HEA of the award and level (bronze, silver or gold) attained by each HEI. As noted in section 4.5, *Second Review of Gender Equality in Irish Higher Education Institutions* (HEA 2022) sets out national minimum requirements for HEIs that include the four Horizon Europe process-related building blocks (i.e., GEP as a public document, dedicated resources allocated for gender equality work, system for collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data in place and planned training and capacity building activities). Evidence that these requirements have been met should be provided to the HEA through annual reporting. In relation to

Horizon Europe GEP-related thematic areas, the HEA gathers data on gender balance in leadership and decision-making; gender equality in recruitment and promotion processes at the institutional level and measures in place against gender-based violence including sexual harassment. Currently, the monitoring system does not gather data on the integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content. The data gathered through the monitoring system is used by the HEA to prepare thematic reports as well as to inform policy decisions.

Taking into consideration the state of play regarding the GEP indicators, clearly this is the area in need of further action by the national authorities as sound monitoring should be connected with the adequate indicators helping to track the dynamics of the change GEPs are contributing to from the national perspective.

5.1.7. Connection to ERA Monitoring

The development of inclusive GEPs is a key instrument and element of a new approach by Member States and the Commission taken to give European Research Area a new impetus and deepen ERA gender equality dimension and commitments in this regard made by MS and AC. This has also been reflected in the Council's conclusions of 1 December 2020 adopted under the German Presidency of the EU Council. These Conclusions called on the Commission and Member States 'for a renewed focus on gender equality and mainstreaming, including through the instrument of gender equality plans and the integration of the gender dimension into R&I content.' (Council of the EU 2020). Monitoring and evaluating national gender equality policies and plans in R&I has, in turn, been a subject tackled by the Council recommendation on the *Pact for research and innovation in Europe* adopted on 26 November 2021 (Council of the EU 2021b). The Pact highlighted the area of policy coordination and monitoring in the context of successful delivery of ERA priorities. In light of the current analysis it seems justified to recall the provision of the Pact that 'the Member States and the Commission should implement an enhanced monitoring mechanism, to ensure a proper basis for evidence-informed policy making in the ERA and to provide evidence and analysis in the context of the European Semester' (Council of the EU 2021b, p. 8). This intertwined relationship between EU and national-level monitoring systems is built on the philosophy of an ERA monitoring mechanism that encompasses, apart from regular policy dialogues between the European Commission and Member States, 'an ERA scoreboard, which monitors progress towards the ERA objectives at Union level, and a more detailed dashboard monitoring progress towards the ERA objectives at national level, through a rich combination of relevant input, outcome and impact indicators and qualitative analyses that accommodate the different circumstances of Member States and that relate to the ERA priorities. The ERA scoreboard should be updated regularly. The ERA scoreboard should assess the overall consolidation and collective progress of ERA priorities and should only display aggregated data at Union level' (Council of the EU 2021b, p. 8).

The GENDERACTIONplus benchmark survey thus inquired if the national monitoring systems related to GEPs are in any way related to ERA monitoring activities. All 6 countries (**Croatia, Greece, Ireland, Norway, Spain, and Sweden**) that have national GEP monitoring systems in place have indicated they are a part of national/regional schemes with only **Greece** pointing out the link of its GEP monitoring system also with the ERA monitoring activities. This indicates the existing national GEPs monitoring frameworks are at not yet linked to the wider ERA monitoring scheme, which is an area in need of further action, undoubtedly, both on the side of the Member and Associated States and the EC.

5.1.8. Public database of GEPs

In 2 out of 6 countries that have national/regional GEP monitoring system there is a public database of GEPs (**Norway** and **Spain**). In case of Norway the Committee for Gender Balance and Diversity in Research (KIF) gathers and publishes all GEPs on a dedicated website.⁸ The comprehensive list of GEPs adopted by the HEIs is in Norwegian, however some universities and university colleges have translated their action plans for gender equality and diversity into English and these are listed on the English version of the website.⁹ As regards Spain, the question on the public database of GEPs was regarded in the context of the biennial report entitled *Científicas en cifras* ('Female scientists in figures') prepared by the Ministry of Science and Innovation through its Women and Science Unit. The report analyses the presence of women in the different science areas and levels in Spain, with special attention to research careers in public research organisations and universities. *Científicas en cifras 2023* includes some indicators on the GEPs of universities and public research organisations. The latest version of the report, with data from 2022, has collected the following information on policies of gender equality:

- number of GEPs in place
- gender equality measures, i.e. measures to promote the integration of the gender dimension in the content of R&I and/or teaching; share of women and men who have participated in GE training; GE training adapted to different groups; balanced representation in decisive bodies; evaluation and monitoring of GEPs; systems for data collection, analysis and dissemination of gender statistics; work-life balance considering? institutional co-responsibility; procedures and or/protocols to guarantee effective equality in selection processes and evaluation; prevention and protection against sexual harassment and gender-based violence; communication and awareness-raising
- gender equality structures: a) the Equality Unit, the Women and Science Unit and the Women, Science and Innovation Observatory within the Ministry of Science and Innovation; b) gender equality units, working groups or observatories to promote and monitor GEPs and GE within public and private HEIs and research organizations.

The data shows that 87% of public and private universities and 60% of public research organizations in Spain had a GEP in place as of 2022. Regarding gender equality structures, there are still limitations: only 28% of public research organizations and 73% of private universities have a gender equality unit (while gender equality structures are in place in almost every public university 94%).

In **Greece**, a *Digital Equality* platform is being developed, which will be a digital repository for the actions and other information concerning the equality committees of the municipalities and regions of the country as well as the gender equality committees of the universities. The actions that will be depicted in the digital equality map will be linked to the four thematic axes of the National Action Plan for Gender Equality.

⁸ <https://kifinfo.no/nb/content/handlingsplaner-likestilling> (retrieved 26 June 2023).

⁹ <https://kifinfo.no/en/content/gender-action-plans> (retrieved 26 June 2023).

5.1.9. Features of GEPs monitored by the national systems

As indicated in the previous sections of the report, the GEP Horizon Europe eligibility criterion exerted noticeable influence on the national R&I gender equality frameworks. As a follow up, our benchmark survey tried to map the congruence of the EU and national systems in terms of the features attributed to Horizon Europe GEP criterion and its reflection in the scope of the national monitoring schemes. The summary of the answers can be found in the table below.

Table 6: Horizon Europe-related GEPs features monitored by national systems

GEPs features	EL	ES	HR	IE	NO	SE
GEP as public document	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Dedicated resources	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Sex/gender-disaggregated data	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Training and capacity building plans	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Gender balance in leadership and decision-making	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Monitoring of gender equality in recruitment and promotion processes at the institutional level	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes
Other	-	-	-	-	Women at grade A	-

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

The **Greek**, **Spanish** and **Swedish** national monitoring systems display the highest level of correspondence with the EU HE GEP content- and process-related building blocks. In case of these countries all of the HE GEPs characteristics listed in the benchmark questions are found to be reflected in the national monitoring systems. **Croatia** and **Ireland** do not monitor the integration of the gender

dimension in research and teaching content with Croatia additionally not monitoring sex/gender disaggregated data and measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment. The Norwegian monitoring system does not include requirements associated with the GEP at the EU level. Instead, HEIs in **Norway** are required to report on women in grade A positions on an annual basis.

5.2. National evaluation systems for GEP implementation

Sweden indicated that a national evaluation system for GEP implementation exists, where the Swedish Agency for Gender Equality is responsible for gathering data and reporting to the government. It should be considered positive that plans toward evaluation system are envisaged in other seven countries: **Austria, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Ireland, Israel, Poland, and Spain**. Experts from **Spain** note that the promotion and assurance of quality is the responsibility shared by the HEIs, the evaluation agencies and the public administrations with competences in this matter. Evaluation agents must have equality measures related to their evaluation processes and, in the case of having more than fifty workers, an equality plan related to their organizations.

In five countries this kind of action is not planned (**Belgium-Wallonia, Denmark, Lithuania, Norway, and Slovakia**), and in some cases there is no knowledge on this matter (**Belgium-Flanders, Greece, and Portugal**). It is important to note that three of them (**Belgium-Flanders, Greece, and Norway**) are countries which have legal GEP requirement in place.

6. EMERGING PRACTICES REGARDING GEP LEGAL PROVISIONS IN NATIONAL FRAMEWORKS AND NATIONAL GEP MONITORING SYSTEMS

This section provides further insights into the national R&I systems and their existing practices regarding GEP requirements as well as GEP monitoring and evaluation measures undertaken by those countries where such measures are in place. The section seeks to develop information presented above in order to provide further guidance in the context of project activities to be developed under the ensuing tasks (for instance task 6.2: Guidance for establishment of GEP monitoring systems). As regards monitoring and evaluation, practices described below apply only to **Norway, Ireland and Spain**.

6.1. Austria

Two kind of equality strategies are stipulated for higher education and R&I institutions – equal opportunity plans and women’s advancement plans. This obligation stems from different legal basis:

- the Federal Equality Act (B-GIBG)¹⁰ and the Universities Act (UG-2022) – for public HEIs¹
- the Higher Education Act (HG) – for university colleges that provide teacher education
- the Private University Act (PrivHG) – for private HEIs
- the University of Applied Sciences Act (FHG) – for universities of applied sciences.

For private HEIs and universities of applied sciences, the accreditation requirement states an obligation to submit a development plan which includes among others equality between women and men and the advancement of women. Private HEIs shall enact the rules of procedure necessary for the fulfilment of their tasks in the form of a published statute, that shall respect the principles of academic autonomy and meet international standards for universities. In particular, the statute shall contain arrangements governing gender equality and the advancement of women. Statutes of universities of applied sciences shall, as a minimum, include an equal opportunities plan, published in a suitable format. Both of these provisions are considered the most significant changes over the last two years in terms of advancing gender equality.

The Federal Equal Treatment Act (B-GIBG) contains detailed information about women's advancement plans. In this B-GIBG act there is a provision that applies to public HEIs: 'The plan for the advancement of women is to be drawn up and updated for a period of six years on the basis of the proportion of women in the total number of permanent employees to be determined as of December 31 of every second year and the expected fluctuation. It must be adapted to current developments every two years'. In case of public RPOs, the Gleichbehandlungsgesetz – GIBG (Equal Treatment Act) is applicable, as it applies to employment relationships of all kinds that are based on a private law contract. So, the Women's advancement requirement and the plan for the advancement of women in the B-GIBG (Federal Equal Treatment Act) are inapplicable to public RPOs. In the National Development Plan for Public Universities 2022–2027 one of the systemic goals is called 'social responsibility of the universities', and one of the important implementation goals within is improvement of social inclusion and diversity-oriented equality. Until 2024 it is assumed implementation of the content of the HEIs' women's advancement plans and equal opportunity plans, including increasing the control relevance of them, and closer integration with the performance agreement.

6.2. Croatia

The Republic of Croatia Act on Gender Equality from 2017 states among others that public administration bodies and legal persons that are majority-owned by the state shall apply specific measures and adopt action plans for the promotion and establishment of gender equality. These bodies shall adopt action plans from their remit on the basis of an analysis of the status of women and men every four years, and they shall establish reasons for the introduction of specific measures, goals to be achieved, method of implementation and implementation control methods. Action plans shall first be approved by the Office for Gender Equality of the Government of the Republic of Croatia. The Act foresees to impose fines for a violation on responsible persons in public bodies and legal persons that

¹⁰ It includes both an obligation to promote women and the prohibition of discrimination against gender, ethnic origin, religion or ideology, age, sexual orientation and the prohibition of gender-related harassment.

are majority-owned by the state who fail to submit, within the period laid, their action plan for the promotion and establishment of gender equality to the Office.

Furthermore, units of local and regional self-government, legal persons with public authorities and legal persons in the business sector, including private companies, crafts businesses and legal persons that are majority-owned by the units of local and regional self-government with more than twenty employees, shall incorporate anti-discrimination provisions and measures with a view to achieving gender equality in their general acts.

In the last two years, adoption of a GEP requirement for all HEIs in the country is considered a crucial change.

6.3. Greece

Until recently, Greece had a law that encouraged, but did not require, institutions to create equality plans. For instance, the law from 2019 on substantive gender equality, prevention and combating gender-based violence states that public and private enterprises are encouraged to draft and implement equality plans with specific targets, strategies and practices. There is also a provision on the General Secretariat for Gender Equality of the Ministry of Interior, which can award 'equality labels' to them as a reward for their engagement in favour of equal treatment and equal opportunities for male and female employees. On the basis of law 4589/2019, so called gender equality committees have been established in all HEIs and research institutions, as advisory bodies for promotion of equality at all levels of operation. One of the most important tasks of the committees is preparation of medium-term action plans. It is worth noting, however, that these bodies set up on a voluntary basis and the GEPs were non-binding and have no impact on public research funding¹¹.

In opinion of Greek respondents to the survey, the adoption of the National Action Plan for gender equality 2021–2025 should be recognised as a turning point. Under the objective 'Promotion of gender equality in education – science – research' two actions are envisaged: mainstreaming the gender dimension at all levels of education and strengthening institutional structures to promote equality. The second action includes monitoring the establishment process of the gender equality committees and monitoring the drafting process of action plans for equality. The indicator for this objective is number of university institutions that have equality plans.

As regards monitoring, in Greece a specific scheme has been proposed that operates at the central, regional and local level. The monitoring of the implementation of the National Plan for Gender Equality 2021-2025 will be done from two points. From the offices of the Deputy Minister of Labor and Social Affairs, responsible for Demographic Policy and the Family and of the General Secretary of Demographic and Family Policy and Gender Equality. At the administrative level, the responsible Department for its monitoring is the Gender Equality Policy Monitoring Department of the Directorate for Planning, Creating Standards and Developing Gender Equality Policies in cooperation with the other

¹¹ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/legislative-policy-backgrounds/greece> (retrieved 26 June 2023).

Directorates as the case may be, as well as with the Regional and Municipal Equality Committees and the contact points at ministerial level designated as equality representatives.

In the context of monitoring the National Action Plan for Gender Equality, the creation of a communication platform accessible to accredited user-members of the agencies is being promoted. This platform aims to highlight initiatives and actions that contribute to the promotion of substantive gender equality and have a positive impact on members of local communities who wish either simply to be informed or to make use of advisory and support services. A helpdesk has been created with the responsibility of strengthening networking and consolidating stable cooperation between the entire institutional mechanism of equality at central and local level.

Furthermore, it is noted that monitoring for the evaluation and implementation of existing equality policies is also done at an institutional level, within the framework of the National Council for Gender Equality. In order to strengthen the consultation and further encourage the dialogue of the involved bodies, the expansion of its members has already been institutionalized with article 20 of Law 4808/2021 (A' 101).

The Observatory for Gender Equality has a particularly important role in monitoring. In order to improve the operation of the Observatory, the upgrading of the information system has already been foreseen, as there is a need to further enrich the data kept and the indicators monitored on an annual basis. This need arises both from the requirements of the Istanbul Convention and from the expansion of the integration of the gender dimension in all sectoral policies at the European level.

Finally, it is planned to create an internal database (platform) to monitor the progress of the implemented projects. Guidelines will be issued to facilitate understanding of the process of monitoring agency equality plans which will concern its mode of operation and the obligations of the ministries for their response to the provisions of Article 10 of Law 4604/2019. The contact details of the contact points of all Ministries will then be requested to be updated and a coordinated communication will be initiated with all the agencies to determine the exact timetable for the implementation of the proposed actions, until the end of 2022.

Finally, the National Plan for Gender Equality is a dynamic text that will be revised annually except for the first year of implementation, i.e. 2021.

6.4. Ireland

Ireland is an example of a country where the topic of gender equality in public higher education is addressed in a holistic way, and which can be seen as a role model for others willing to move in a similar direction. The main actor responsible for policy-making is the Higher Education Authority (HEA). This body funds the Athena Swan Ireland Charter, launched in 2015 with a specific remit to encourage and recognise commitment to advancing the careers of women in science, which has since expanded to include all disciplines, and all categories of HEI staff. Bronze, silver and gold awards are awarded to confirm success of institutions and departments in the areas of gender equality¹². HEIs without an

¹² <https://hea.ie/policy/gender/athena-swain> [access 24 March 2023].

Athena Swan Charter Institution level award are ineligible for public research funding (EU-CONEXUS 2002, p. 9).

Advance HE (who runs the Athena Swan process in Ireland) notify the HEA of the award level attained by each institution. The Athena Swan award indicates that all requirements have been met, a GEP is in place and has been reviewed independently. Many of the Athena Swan Charter Ireland requirements align directly with Horizon Europe GEP requirements, which is also reflected in national policy monitoring requirements. An updated Athena Swan Ireland Charter Framework was launched at the end of 2021. Consultations held during this process stressed the need to align the Athena Swan Action Plans with the requirements set by Horizon Europe. Advance HE (2022) have issued guidance aimed at colleagues developing and implementing institutional GEPs on how to use the Athena Swan Ireland charter framework to assist them in meeting the Horizon Europe Gender Equality Plan requirements.

In 2016, the HEA conducted the *First HEA National Gender Equality Review of Irish Higher Education Institutions*. To ensure sustainable progress towards gender equality, both the HEA Expert Group and the Gender Equality Taskforce recommended reviews of progress at the end of the lifespan of their recommendations. The Minister for Higher Education established the Gender Equality Taskforce to identify significant measures that could accelerate progress in achieving gender equality in Irish HEIs. Actions recommended by the Taskforce (HEA 2017) in the *Gender Action Plan 2018-2020* were:

- all HEIs shall set ambitious short, medium and long-term targets (one, three and five years) for the proportion of people of each gender which it aims to have at senior levels of academic and professional, management and support staff across the institution
- all HEIs shall set ambitious short, medium and long-term goals and actions at institutional level in order to progress gender equality
- all HEIs shall submit their institutional gender equality plan to the HEA and provide annual progress updates
- the institutional GEP shall be implemented through discipline / business unit GEP
- HEA block grant funding shall be linked to an institution's performance in addressing gender inequality through the strategic dialogue process and System Performance Framework
- a new 'Gender Equality Enhancement Funding Call' should be set up to support innovative organisational and cultural change initiatives nationally
- a new Centre of Excellence for Gender Equality, with a dedicated resource, shall be established by the department under the auspice of the HEA. The Centre shall: (1) ensure sustainable acceleration towards gender equality in HEIs; (2) foster HEI collaboration and disseminate good practice; (3) provide centralised support for HEIs; (4) report regularly to the Minister in relation to performance of the system.

In line with the recommendation of 2016 Report the HEA, along with an external Expert Group, conducted a *Second Gender Equality Review of Irish Higher Education Institutions* over the course of 2022. The Review has assessed the progress made since the 2016 Review and the perception of gender equality among HEI staff and make recommendations to ensure the continued advancement of gender equality in the higher education sector. The Review was undertaken in close partnership with the higher education sector and in consultation with relevant stakeholders.

According to the second review, significant progress in many institutions was noticeable, although varied for different indicators. This progress resulted from the engagement of many stakeholders,

governmental and institutional investments, and invaluable efforts of many individuals (HEA 2022, p. 6). To advance this process, the HEA Expert Group recommendations for all Irish HEIs are (ibid., p. 29):

- to have an institutional GEP that is published on the HEI website, signed by the president, actively communicated and progress monitored within the institution
- to demonstrate a commitment to provide sufficient resources and expertise in gender equality, particularly in relation to the implementation of its institutional GEP
- to have a vice-president (or equivalent) with responsibility for equality, diversity and inclusion
- to collect and analyse sex/gender-disaggregated data on staff to inform the institutional strategy for advancement of gender equality
- to provide training towards sustaining the advancement of gender equality for all staff
- to provide evidence that these requirements have been met to the HEA through annual reporting.

The *Gender Action Plan 2018–2020* envisaged that ‘by 2026 Ireland will be a world leading country for gender equality in higher education’ (HEA 2017, p. 5). In 2022, the European Commission launched a new prize recognising academic and research organisations driving the change towards gender equality in research and innovation. The winners of the first edition of the prize were announced on International Women’s Day, 8 March 2023. Three out of the four institutions awarded prizes are from Ireland¹³:

1. **Sustainable gender equality champions:** organisations that demonstrated a significant and sustained record of activity and a high level of achievement through the implementation of their GEP: **Trinity College Dublin (Ireland) and Karolinska Institutet in Solna (Sweden).**
2. **Newcomer gender equality champions:** organisations that had recently started implementing a GEP and can demonstrate the most progress in its implementation and achieved result: **Maynooth University (Ireland).**
3. **Inclusive gender equality champions:** organisations that had developed the most innovative inclusive GEP addressing intersections with other social categories such as ethnicity, social origin, sexual orientation, gender identity, disability: **South East Technological University (Ireland).**

As noted in section 5.1, in terms of GEPs features that are monitored by the Irish monitoring system, these are all of the four Horizon Europe process-related building blocks, i.e., GEP as a public document, dedicated resources allocated for gender equality work, system for collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data in place and planned training and capacity building activities. In terms of Horizon Europe GEP-related thematic areas, Irish monitoring system gathers data on: gender balance in leadership and decision-making; gender equality in recruitment and promotion processes at the institutional level and measures in place against gender-based violence including sexual harassment. What is worth noting, the current monitoring system implemented in Ireland does not gather data on the integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content. The data gathered through the monitoring system is used by the responsible authority to prepare thematic reports as well as to inform policy decisions.

¹³ https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/prizes/eu-award-gender-equality-champions_en (retrieved 26 June 2023).

6.5. Norway

The employer's activity and reporting duty applies to all universities, colleges and research institutes in Norway. The extent of the duty varies between small and large, public and private enterprises.

In line with the Equality and Anti-discrimination Act,¹⁴ all public universities and colleges and all private universities, colleges and institutes with more than 50 employees shall make active, targeted and systematic efforts to ensure gender equality and fulfil the reporting duty in this regard. This means that they shall issue a statement on equality measures implemented or planned, to promote the purpose of this Act. The current state of gender equality in the institution and the work done to meet the requirements of the activity duty need to be included, and every other year institutions are required to issue a statement on the gender pay gap, involuntary part-time employment and the gender distribution of different position levels (KIF 2023). Private institutes with fewer than 20 employees are only covered by the general duty to prevent discrimination and promote equality across the entire breadth of personnel policy. This work must nevertheless be documented. For research institutes with between 20 and 50 employees, extended activity and reporting duties apply if one of the parties requires it. A party is defined as the management, union representative or the majority of the employees. If this is not required, the general duty applies.¹⁵

Table 7: Reporting duties for different types of employers in Norway

Type of institution	General duty	Specific activity duty	Reporting duty
Public	Yes	Yes	Yes
Private with more than 50 employees	Yes	Yes	No
Private with between 20 and 50 employees	Yes	If one of the parties requires it	
Private with less than 20 employees	Yes	No	No

Source: own analysis based on responses to the benchmark survey.

What is more, the University and University Colleges Act states that HEIs shall make active, targeted and systematic efforts to ensure gender equality in all categories of employment at the institution. The Equality and Anti-Discrimination Ombud has in its duty to monitor and evaluate GEPs. Data on the status

¹⁴ It is the main national anti-discrimination/equal opportunity law in Norway. It entered into force on 1 January 2018 replacing four previous acts (<https://lovdata.no/dokument/NLE/lov/2017-06-16-51>, retrieved 26 June 2023).

¹⁵ Detailed guidelines can be found on the Equality and Antidiscrimination Ombud website (<https://www.ldo.no/en/jobbe-for-likestilling/i-arbeidslivet/Aktivitets-og-redegjorelsesplikten/employers-activity-duty-and-the-duty-to-issue-a-statement>, retrieved 26 June 2023).

of gender equality and diversity in research is included in annual and biannual statistics reports such as the report on science and technology indicators for Norway (annual) and status report on higher education (biannual).

It is worth mentioning that the Norwegian database on statistics on higher education has its own site on gender, along with gender disaggregated data on different parameters in research.¹⁶ The Committee for Gender Balance and Diversity in Research (KIF) undertakes an annual review of which Norwegian institutions from the sector of higher education and research and innovation have a GEP¹⁷.

Following the requirements in the Horizon Europe, also the Research Council of Norway has introduced a GEP as an eligibility requirement for applicants and partners that must be met when the grant agreement is signed. This applies to calls for proposals with a deadline for applications in 2022 or later.

As a result of all actions that are undertaken, every higher education institution in Norway has a gender equality plan in place (as of February 2023).

The Norwegian system of GEP monitoring is based on the reports with gender-disaggregated data on research careers, including on women in grade A positions, and students. These reports are commissioned by the Ministry of Education and Research on an annual basis and every other year data is gathered on equal pay (gender pay gap). The requirement to submit the above-mentioned data applies to public and private sector, more precisely to all public organisations, regardless of size, and private undertakings with more than 50 employees. The data is gathered by the KIF which is also responsible for publication of all GEPs that exist for HEIs in Norway. As far as the scope of the monitoring is concerned, all required employers have a duty to report on the state of play referring to the following aspects:

- the current state of affairs with regard to gender equality in the undertaking;
- equality measures implemented or planned to promote the purpose of the Norwegian Equality and Anti-discrimination Act referring to the equality, irrespective of gender¹⁸.

In addition to that, all required employers shall issue a statement on equality measures implemented or planned to promote the Act's purpose of equality irrespective of ethnicity, religion, belief, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity and gender expression.

The data collected through annual reports is used as an input to the state budget which includes a chapter with data on gender equality in academia. More precisely, the state budget presents data on

¹⁶ <https://kifinfo.no/en/content/statistics> (retrieved 26 June 2023).

¹⁷ https://kifinfo.no/sites/default/files/building_blocks_national_requirements_norway.pdf (retrieved 26 June 2023).

¹⁸ In line with section 26: *All employers shall, in their operations, make active, targeted and systematic efforts to promote equality and prevent discrimination on the basis of gender, pregnancy, leave in connection with childbirth or adoption, care responsibilities, ethnicity, religion, belief, disability, sexual orientation, gender identity and gender expression. Such efforts shall encompass recruitment, pay and working conditions, promotion, development opportunities, accommodation, the opportunity to combine work with family life and preventing harassment. All public undertakings, regardless of size, and private undertakings that ordinarily employ more than 50 persons shall, in the context of their operations: a) investigate whether there is a risk of discrimination or other barriers to equality; b) analyse the causes of identified risks; c) implement measures suited to counteract discrimination and promote greater equality and diversity in the undertaking, and d) evaluate the results of efforts made pursuant to a) and c).*

female PhD students, female professors and men and women in fulltime and part-time positions. There is also data on country background of faculty at different universities.

6.6. Spain

For Spanish institutions a strong impetus for the development of GEPs was the Organic Law on Effective Equality between Women and Men from 2007¹⁹. This law states that organisations are obliged to prepare and implement equality plans, following negotiation or consultation with female and male workers. The equality plans will establish the specific equality objectives to be achieved, the strategies and practices to be adopted for their attainment, as well as the establishment of effective systems for monitoring and evaluating the objectives set. GEPs should also contain an orderly set of assessable measures aimed at removing obstacles that prevent or hinder the effective equality of women and men. The following issues should be addressed: (1) selection and recruitment process; (2) professional classification; (3) training; (4) career development; (5) working conditions, including wage audit between women and men; (6) co-responsible exercise of personal, family and working life rights; (7) under-representation of women; (8) remuneration; (9) prevention of sexual and gender-based harassment. Equality plans shall be recorded in a special register. At the beginning of each legislative term, the government shall approve a gender equality plan in the General State Administration and in the public bodies linked to or dependent on it. The Plan shall establish the objectives to be achieved with regard to the promotion of equal treatment and opportunities in public employment, as well as the strategies or measures to be adopted to achieve them.

The Organic Law on Universities, also with the provisions from 2007, stimulated establishment of gender equality structures and policies at Spanish universities. In the preamble one can read: 'The challenge of today's society to achieve a tolerant and egalitarian society, in which fundamental rights and freedoms are respected and equality between men and women, must undoubtedly reach the university'. The main goals were:

- to establish systems which allow to achieve parity in the bodies of representation and greater participation of women in research groups
- to remove the obstacles that prevent women from participating in the governing bodies of HEIs and reaching the highest career level in public teaching and research, in line with the percentage of university graduates by gender
- to create specific programmes on gender equality.

The newest Organic Law of the University System (2/2023, of March 22), which entered into force on 12 April 2023, states setting up gender equality requirements prior to the establishment of a HEI, such as equality plans, or the elimination of pay gap and all forms of harassment. Under the provisions of the Act HEI bodies and evaluation and selection committees shall guarantee a balanced composition between women and men, positive action measures in competitions and for conciliation, and the promotion of shared responsibility for care, among many other measures. One of the functions of the

¹⁹ The Organic Law on Effective Equality between Women and Men (2007), together with the Comprehensive Law for Equal Treatment and Non-discrimination (2022) are the two main national anti-discrimination and equal opportunity laws in Spain.

governing council, the highest governing bodies in the HEIs, is to define and promote GEPs for the entire academic community. What is more, equality measures and GEPs play an important role in the HEIs evaluation process.

As regards national GEP monitoring, Spain does not consider itself to have national GEP monitoring system as such but rather a constructive dialogue with the institutions involved in the coordination of gender equality policies. The agents of the Spanish Science, Technology and Innovation system that form part of the state public sector are required, by law, to have GEPs in the field of research, development and innovation with programmes and measures envisioned to support and promote actions for effective equality, as described in more detail in the section above. In addition to that, protocols against sexual harassment and gender-based harassment have to be developed and they are monitored on an annual basis. The agents of Spanish research, development and innovation system are also required to have protocols against harassment based on sexual orientation, gender identity and sexual characteristics.

There are three major units involved in the gender equality R&I-related activities on the part of the national authorities. First, the Women and Science Unit of the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation is responsible for the coordination of the gender equality policies of research public organisms dependent on the Ministry as well as for the design of initiatives at the national level, that are guided by the reform of the Spanish Law of Science, Technology, and Innovation (2022), the upcoming GEP for R&I, and other initiatives promoted by the Ministry of R&I such as mentoring and a scheme award. The Women and Science Unit is also responsible for drafting *Científicas en cifras* biennial report. Second, the Equality Unit of the Spanish Ministry of Universities is responsible for the coordination of the gender equality policies of universities, which are guided by the Organic Law of Universities and the initiatives promoted by the Ministry of Universities. And third, the Observatory for Women, Science and Innovation, regulated by Royal Decree 938/2020 of October 27, which is an inter-ministerial body responsible for analyzing, monitoring and measuring impacts, as well as proposing, advising and promoting the implementation of public policies and actions to advance towards gender equality in the field of R+D+I.

An important tool for monitoring GE measures in place in R&I sector, including GEP-related characteristics, is the above-mentioned report. The latest edition of *Científicas en cifras* report (Women and Science Unit 2023, p. 117) analyses inter alia the presence of gender equality policies in universities (public and private) and public research organizations as well as the existence of Gender Equality Plans (the report states that GEPs are usually developed through measures and actions aimed at equality, however, the situation may also arise in which there are entities that develop and implement measures to advance in equality, without the measures being part of a plan). Among the types of gender equality measures that have been analyzed there is existence of specific gender equality units or working groups for the evaluation and monitoring of the GEPs. In relation to public universities, units or specific working groups on gender equality for the evaluation and monitoring of GEPs were established in 96% of them. As regards the existence of similar monitoring structures on the GEPs in private universities, these have been implemented in more than 80% of them. In the public research organizations, monitoring structures exist in 72% of this type of institutions (ibid., p. 118). Monitoring of GEPs is actually one of the actions where the Women and Science Unit recommends to take action to improve the situation regarding the gender equality structures.

6.7. Sweden

The three legal requirements for HEIs, RPOs and RFOs are the general Discrimination Act (2008), the Swedish Higher Education Act (1992), and the Higher Education Ordinance (1993). According to initial provisions of the first one: 'Equality between women and men shall always be taken into account and promoted in the operations of higher education institutions. Employers are obliged to work on active measures that encompass working conditions, provisions and practices regarding pay and other terms of employment, recruitment and promotion, education and training, and other skills development, and possibilities to reconcile gainful employment and parenthood. It means pursuing prevention and promotion work by (1) investigating the existence of any risks of discrimination or reprisals or any other obstacles to individuals' equal rights and opportunities in the establishment in question; (2) analysing the causes of any risks and obstacles discovered; (3) taking the prevention and promotion measures that can reasonably be demanded, and (4) monitoring and evaluating measures. It is stated also that work on active measures has to be conducted continuously, and that measures should be scheduled and implemented as soon as possible.

In detail, employers are obliged to promote gender balance in different types of work, among different categories of employees and in management positions by means of education and training, skills development and other appropriate measures. They shall also conduct annual surveys to analyse provisions and practices regarding salaries and other dimensions of employment, and to assess association of potential differences with gender.

Special place in the Act is dedicated to education providers, in case of which active measures encompass: (1) admission and recruitment procedures; (2) teaching methods and organisation of education; (3) examinations and assessments of students' performance; (4) study environment; and (5) possibilities to reconcile studies with parenthood. Education providers are to have guidelines and routines for their activities, with a view to preventing harassment and sexual harassment, and have to follow up and evaluate the guidelines and routines in place. As for monitoring, they are obliged to annual documenting in writing their work on active measures.

Providing guidelines and carrying out inspections of GEPs is a task of the government agency on gender equality and anti-discrimination in the labour market – the Equality Ombudsman (Diskriminerings Ombudsmannen, DO). The Gender Equality Agency (Jämställdhetsmyndigheten) supports HEIs inter alia at the planning and implementation equality activities. Working on gender mainstreaming is an important task of higher education and research institutions, according to the special development programme the Gender Mainstreaming in Academic (*Jämställdhetsintegrering i högskolor och universitet*), with such priorities as equal and non-stereotypical career paths and improving the throughput of women and men in education. In accordance with the provisions of the directive U2020/02952, all HEIs shall continue gender mainstreaming work and describe it in development plans (i.e., reporting measures and results, considering gender equality in the distribution of research funds).

7. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This report demonstrates that Gender Equality Plans are mandatory in the majority of the countries/regions participating in the survey and the GEP requirement applies predominantly to public sector entities. GEPs national requirements (or the lack thereof) are testament to the persistent divide between the Member States that joined the EU before and after 2004. For post-2004 MS, RFOs can significantly contribute to creating favourable framework conditions for GEP development.

Additionally, intersectionality is an underdeveloped area in regard to GEP requirements. There is evidence of challenges in relation to the inclusion of dimensions other than gender in GEP development and elaboration of effective measures against inequalities running along different axes (Korsvik, González, and Dvorackova 2023; Holt Zachariassen, Ghosh, and Woods 2023). These can be attributed to a lack of in-depth knowledge about intersectionality coupled with the difficulty in understanding the term and GDPR restrictions.

The Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion exerted noticeable impact on national gender equality activities in R&I, which is demonstrated particularly by the increase in approved GEPs in R&I institutions, the organisation of workshops and trainings on GEPs, dedication of resources for gender equality work and an increase in requests addressed to the National Contact Points (e.g., queries in relation to GEP elaboration or EC requirements). However, a limited influence of Horizon Europe GEP criterion is to be seen on opening new actions associated with GEP content-related areas in R&I institutions as well as national funding for GEP development.

The findings of this report demonstrate that national monitoring and evaluation systems for GEPs are a key challenge that is augmented by the increasing number of GEPs in higher education and R&I institutions. The data collected through the monitoring systems greatly varies between the countries, together with their approach to publicly available GEPs database and elaboration of monitoring indicators. Despite limitations in the existence of national monitoring systems, the countries with such systems in place display a high degree of correspondence between Horizon Europe GEP features and structures monitored through national schemes. National evaluation systems for GEPs implementation are not widespread yet are considered to be established in the number of countries/ participating in the survey. This finding points to the existence of different definitions or interpretations of monitoring across different countries.

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APPENDIX A – BENCHMARK SURVEY QUESTIONS FOR NATIONAL AUTHORITIES

Below is the benchmarking survey targeted at national authorities (ministries, national agencies and organisations that support them). Please note that for the purpose of the benchmarking analysis of monitoring/evaluation of GEPs the following sections of the benchmarking survey have been taken into consideration: **Section 9: GEP monitoring / Evaluating GEP impact** and **Section 4.9: The effect of Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion on gender equality in research & innovation in the surveyed country.**

GENDERACTIONplus: BENCHMARKING OF NATIONAL/REGIONAL POLICIES

Scope and objective: This is a benchmarking exercise of national (and regional as relevant) policies on gender equality in research, higher education and innovation (NP on GE in RHEI) and focuses on the five thematic areas of GENDERACTIONplus (intersectionality and inclusiveness; gender-based violence; gender dimension in research, innovation and teaching; monitoring and evaluation in the ERA; institutional change through gender equality plans). The objective is to establish what is in place in each country and what are emerging good practices we can learn from.

Background: In 2021, gender equality in higher education, research and innovation has been reaffirmed as a priority for the new European Research Area (ERA).²⁰ By end of June 2022, Member States have indicated their interest in addressing ERA Action 5 (Gender equality and inclusiveness). New policy areas identified include intersectionality and inclusiveness and gender-based violence in academia. Further policy attention is required in the areas of the gender dimension in teaching, research and innovation; monitoring and evaluation of ERA policies and advancing institutional change through Gender Equality Plans, including monitoring and evaluation of the impact of GEPs on gender equality.

This benchmark is to set ground for current policies and developments at the national and regional level as relevant. As such, it will be an important contribution to ERA Policy Action 5 as the project is expected to provide policy input and advice on ERA Policy Action 5.

We kindly request all partners to provide as full answers as possible, including the links to potential policy documents and translations of the relevant text of the policy. Not answering a question or not providing information about policies when they are in place should be a last resort. Thank you!

With this benchmark, information is pursued that is not obtainable in other ways and hence the contribution of the project partners is vital.

²⁰ Communication from the Commission A new ERA for Research and Innovation ([COM/2020/628 final](#)); Council Conclusions on the New European Research Area of 1 December 2020 ([13567/20](#)); Council Conclusions on the future governance of the European Research Area ([14308/21](#)); The Ljubljana Declaration on Gender Equality in Research and Innovation (available [here](#)); [EU Pact for Research and Innovation](#).

Timeframe: 2017 – present time unless specified otherwise; the focus is on policies that are in force now and recent evolution

Who should complete: One answer per country is requested. Project partners (both beneficiaries and Associated Partners) are responsible for coordinating input to the benchmark with other relevant national bodies (as the case may be). Given the cooperation may be required between different national authorities or responsible persons in completing the benchmark survey, the questionnaire can be downloaded and shared as a .doc file. **The deadline for providing your input in the LimeSurvey is 6 November 2022.**

Main definitions

- **Law** is a set of rules that are created and enforceable by social or governmental institutions to regulate behaviour, adopted through a defined legislative process.
- **Policy** is a deliberate system of guidelines to guide decisions and achieve outcomes. It is a statement of intent and is implemented as a procedure or protocol. Policies are generally adopted by a governance body within an organization. For the purpose of this benchmark, policies are defined as adopted by national or regional governments in the form of official regulations, and procedures officially adopted by the governing body in the form of a document.
- **Policy measure** is an action taken by the national / regional authority that may be one-off, not embedded in a policy document and agreed.

A [glossary](#) is attached providing definitions of key concepts.

Notes:

- **in the case of requests for document translations to English, if there is/are no official document(s), machine translation(s) is/are sufficient;**
- **otherwise, an official institutional position is sought unless requested explicitly otherwise.**

There are 158 questions in this survey.

1. Background information

1.1 Partner institution

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Bundesministerium für Bildung, Wissenschaft und Forschung
- Danish Agency for Higher Education and Science + Independent Research Fund Denmark (DFF)
- Departement Economy, Science and Innovation
- Deutsches Zentrum für Luft
- Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología (FECYT)
- Goeteborgs Universitet
- Higher Education Authority
- Institute for Advanced Studies
- Institute of Sociology of the Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic
- Joanneum Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH
- Kunnskapsdepartementet
- Malta Council for Science and Technology (MCST)
- Maynooth University
- Ministry of Education, Science And Sport (MIZS)
- Ministry of Education, Science and Sport of the Republic of Lithuania
- Ministry of Innovation, Science & Technology (MOST)
- Ministry of Science and Education (MZO)
- Ministry of the Wallonia-Brussels Federation
- National Commission for the Promotion of Equality
- National Documentation Centre
- National Information Processing Institute
- Syddansk Universitet
- Univerzita Mateja Bela
- Vetenskap & Allmanhet (Va)
- Vilnius University Šiauliai Academy

1.2 Country

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- AT
- BE-Flanders
- BE-FWB
- CZ
- DE
- DK
- EL
- ES

- HR
- IE
- IL
- LT
- MT
- NO
- PL
- SE
- SI
- SK

1.3 Contact person for the benchmarking exercise (the person to be potentially contacted in the event supplementary information is needed).

Please write your answer here:

1.4 Email

Please write your answer here:

1.5 Main responsible national authority responding to the benchmark:

Please write your answer here:

1.6 Other national authorities contributing to the benchmark completion *

Please write your answer here:

1.7 Method of benchmark completion (please comment on the process of data and information gathering; especially for partners appointed by national authorities, comment on whether the answers reflect your expert assessment or whether they reflect the official position of the national authorities you have been appointed to represent in the project).

Please write your answer here:

2. National/regional anti-discrimination and/or equality laws and policies

This section serves to establish the existence of the main national laws and policies on gender equality / anti-discrimination / equal opportunities.

2.1 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination and/or equal opportunity laws?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a name and link to the main national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity law if relevant (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

For example, in the Czech Republic, this would be the [Antidiscrimination Act](#); this question is NOT asking about the law on higher education.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '8 [B21]' (2.1 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination and/or equal opportunity laws?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s) and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '8 [B21]' (2.1 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination and/or equal opportunity laws?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

2.2 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity policy?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a name and link to the national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity policy (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

For example, in the Czech Republic, this would be the [Gender Equality Strategy for 2021 – 2030](#); this question is NOT about the higher education policy or research, development and innovation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '11 [B22]' (2.2 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity policy?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s) and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '11 [B22]' (2.2 Does your country have a national/regional anti-discrimination / equal opportunity policy?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

3. New European Research Area (ERA)

Previous ERA National Action Plans (NAPs) have been particularly successful when based on a broad commitment. This section therefore seeks to establish the process through which the national authorities have determined the actions to sign up for in the new ERA.

3.1 Has the process of identifying the new ERA Actions to sign up for been participatory (e.g., organised events such as round tables or consultations with relevant stakeholders)?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify who has been involved in the process including the departments/units responsible for gender equality/diversity/equal opportunities.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '14 [C31]' (3.1 Has the process of identifying the new ERA Actions to sign up for been participatory (e.g., organised events such as round tables or consultations with relevant stakeholders)?)

Please write your answer here:

3.2 Do the ERA Action 5 topics included in the national response build on existing policy priorities and actions?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, which ones (such as national policy, the previous ERA NAPs):

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '16 [C32]' (3.2 Do the ERA Action 5 topics included in the national response build on existing policy priorities and actions?)

Please write your answer here:

4. Overall assessment of gender equality laws and policies in higher education and research

This section serves to assess the existence of laws and policies specifically on gender equality in higher education and research and innovation and establish whether it is a priority for the national / regional authorities, who is responsible and what the most recent developments are.

As an example, the Czech Republic does not have a specific law or policy on gender equality in higher education and/or research so will answer 'No' to 4.1 and 4.2. There is a [National RDI Policy Czech](#)

[Republic 2021+](#) which addresses equality and work-life balance and there is [Gender Equality Strategy 2021-2030](#) which has a section dedicated to Knowledge (education and research). Hence, the answer will be 'Yes' to 4.2.2 and these two documents would be provided.

4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

4.1.1 If yes, which bodies/authorities are responsible for implementing the law?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please write your answer here:

4.1.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived law on higher education, law on research and innovation or equality law?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify. Please provide a name and link (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '20 [D412]' (4.1.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived law on higher education, law on research and innovation or equality law?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '20 [D412]' (4.1.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived law on higher education, law on research and innovation or equality law?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

4.2.1 If yes, which institution/s are responsible for implementing the policy?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please write your answer here:

4.2.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived policy on higher education, policy on research and innovation or their combination or equality policy?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages and if not in English, provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '25 [D422]' (4.2.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived policy on higher education, policy on research and innovation or their combination or equality policy?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document, specify the relevant passages and if not in English, provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '25 [D422]' (4.2.2 If no, is gender equality in higher education and/or research and innovation addressed in a more broadly conceived policy on higher education, policy on research and innovation or their combination or equality policy?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

4.3 What are the most important policy developments at the national / regional level (as relevant) on gender equality in RHEI in the last two years (e.g., adoption of whole new policy, adoption of

a policy framework on fighting gender-based violence in higher education, adoption of a GEP requirement for all HEIs in the country etc.)?

Please write your answer here:

4.4 What have been the main facilitating factors for these developments?

Please write your answer here:

4.5a Please provide a name and link to the new developments at the national / regional level in question 4.3. Please provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Please write your answer here:

4.5b If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s) (please provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation).

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

4.6 What have been the main hindering factors for advancing gender equality policy in RHEI?

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Resistance at institutional level
- Lack of economic resources
- Lack of human resources
- Lack of interest
- Not regarded as relevant
- Lack of research-based knowledge and data
- Other:

4.7 Have any policies / actions / activities been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

4.7.1 If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '33 [D47]' (4.7 Have any policies / actions / activities been discontinued in the last five years due to budgetary constraints?)

Please write your answer here:

4.8 Have any policies / actions / activities been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

4.8.1 If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '35 [D48]' (4.8 Have any policies / actions / activities been discontinued in the last five years due to political reasons?)

Please write your answer here:

4.9 Specifically, to what extent has the [Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion](#) had an effect on gender equality in research & innovation in your country?

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- To no extent
- To little extent
- To some extent
- To a large extent
- To a very large extent

4.9.1 What concrete effect the GEP requirement has had?

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- New GEPs have been approved in R&I institutions
- Workshops and training have been organised in the R&I field on GEPs at the national level
- An increase in requests/questions received by NCPs as a result of the eligibility criterion
- The EC recommended thematic areas have opened new lines of action in R&I institutions
- New tools and material developed on developing and implementing GEPs in R&I
- Increased national funding for GEP development
- Other:

4.9.2 Additional comment (please provide any other relevant information about the effect of the GEP requirement or discussions surrounding it that will help to better understand and contextualise the information provided in the survey). Please add NA if not applicable.

Please write your answer here:

5. Intersectionality

The Commission has stated a wish to broaden gender equality policies in research and innovation to intersections with other potential grounds for discrimination such as ethnicity, disability and sexual

orientation. This section of the survey serves to assess to what extent this is addressed in EU Member States and Associated Countries.

5.1 Does the national/regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation address one or more of the following dimensions?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

Please provide a link to this law and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.2 Is this a recent development (last 3-5 years)?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.3 If you do not have a national/regional law on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in a more broadly conceived national/regional law for higher education, research and innovation?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '18 [D41]' (4.1 Do you have a national/ regional law for higher education and/ or research and innovation that includes gender equality?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '44 [E53]' (5.3 If you do not have a national/regional law on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in a more broadly conceived national/regional law for higher education, research and innovation?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document, specify the relevant passages, and if not in English, provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '44 [E53]' (5.3 If you do not have a national/regional law on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in a more broadly conceived national/regional law for higher education, research and innovation?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.4 If you have a national/regional policy on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, does this policy also address one or more of the following dimensions?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age

- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- None
- Other:

5.5 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality covered in your policy and initiatives, what are the terms most frequently used? Please tick all that apply:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Non-discrimination
- Intersectionality
- Representation
- Gender+ equality
- Diversity
- Inclusiveness/inclusion
- Inclusive equality
- Equity/equality
- Other:

Please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please write your answer here:

Or please upload the document, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.6 If you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is this a recent development (last 3-5 years)?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide examples. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.7.1 Does this policy also address one or more of the following dimensions. Please tick all that apply:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

5.7.2 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality covered in your policy, what are the terms most frequently used? Please tick all that apply: *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Non-discrimination
- Intersectionality
- Representation
- Gender+ equality
- Diversity
- Inclusiveness/inclusion
- Inclusive equality
- Equity/equality
- None of the above
- Other:

Please provide a link, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

5.7.3 Is the inclusion of the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.) a recent development (last 3-5 years)?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '52 [E57]' (5.7 If you do not have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country, is the topic of equality, diversity and inclusion addressed in more broadly conceived national/regional policies or strategies for higher education and research and innovation (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.8 Has your ministry or any other relevant national/regional authority faced any of the following obstacles in developing a policy including an intersectional approach? Please tick all that apply.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Uncertainty about the terminology to be used
- Lack of a unified understanding of the underlying concepts
- Gender equality as a policy topic is a struggle without other inequality grounds
- Resistance at higher education/research institutions

- Legal regulations restricting data collection (e.g., personal data protection)
- Lack of human resources
- Lack of economic resources
- Lack of interest / not regarded to be relevant
- Lack of disaggregated data on ethnic and other minorities
- Lack of research-based knowledge on gender and diversity in research in your country
- None
- Other:

5.9 Do you have national measures to support the implementation of inclusive/ intersectional policies in research?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '23 [D42]' (4.2 Do you have a national/regional policy specifically on gender equality for higher education and/or research and innovation in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

5.9.1 If yes, please tick all that apply:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '61 [E59]' (5.9 Do you have national measures to support the implementation of inclusive/ intersectional policies in research?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Reporting to national authorities on gender balance indicators
- Reporting to national authorities on indicators on other grounds of inequality (ethnicity, socio-economic status, age, disability etc.)
- National conferences
- Financial incentives (e.g., support to institutions for recruiting women in STEMM)
- Advisory centres for gender equality
- National committees appointed by ministries or other national bodies
- National awareness-raising campaigns
- Other:

5.10 What initiatives and knowledge are needed to lift the intersection of gender equality with other dimensions of diversity on the policy agenda at your ministry and on the policy agenda in the European Research Area? Please tick all that apply:

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Mutual learning initiatives
- Clear guidelines from the EC

- Advanced legal framework at national level
- Financial incentives and support
- Research commissioned on how to address the intersection of gender equality with other potential grounds of discrimination
- I don't know
- Other:

6. Inclusive research careers

The purpose of Section 6 is to map current and emerging strategies and policies on research careers. Through the information collected and analysed - pinpointing patterns, gaps and solutions, and deepening evidence-based knowledge - we will be able to develop strategic policy recommendations in order to promote more inclusive careers across MS and AC, careers conceived through the intersectional perspective. This converges with the challenge of building the new ERA, in line with the [Council Conclusions Deepening the European Research Area: Providing researchers with attractive and sustainable careers and working conditions and making brain circulation a reality](#), [Pact for Research and Innovation in Europe](#) and the [ERA Policy Agenda](#) (especially at the crossroad of Actions 4 and 5).

6.1 Are there national strategies/policies/policy measures in place, specifically focused on research careers in higher education and research and innovation institutions in your country?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '64 [F61]' (6.1 Are there national strategies/policies/policy measures in place, specifically focused on research careers in higher education and research and innovation institutions in your country?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify (provide a link to the document online, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify (provide a link to the document online, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please tick all that apply:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

Please, identify the strategies/policies/policy instruments, provide links and quote the exact references to the policies in 6.1 and 6. 2. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

6.3 Is attention to inclusive research careers in national policies or strategies a recent development (less than 3 years) or an established area of work (more than 3 years)? Please specify.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '75 [F63]' (6.3 Is attention to inclusive research careers in national policies or strategies a recent development (less than 3 years) or an established area of work (more than 3 years)? Please specify.)

Please write your answer here:

6.4 What do the inclusive measures of these strategies/policies/policy initiatives focus on? Tick all that apply:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Gender equality
- Gender bias
- Equal access to employment
- Career progression (including recruiting women to professorship and/ or academic leadership)
- Job Precarity
- Gender pay-gap
- Early careers
- Nonlinear careers
- International mobility
- Intersectoral mobility
- Interdisciplinary mobility

- Portability of social security
- Work-life balance
- Working conditions
- Skills and employability
- Professional visibility /recognition
- Research assessment
- Other:

Please add a short text to explain the context and content of all the previously selected measures in 6.4

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?)

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

6.4.1 Has Research Assessment been a topic before the launch of the [Reforming Research Assessment Initiative](#) and under action 3 of the European Research Area Policy Agenda?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '77 [F64]' (6.4 What do the inclusive measures of these strategies/policies/policy initiatives focus on? Tick all that apply:)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

6.4.2 Do any of the criteria for research assessment address gender inequality or other grounds of discrimination (across disciplines, research types, career stages, research roles, peer review, training and mentoring, other...)?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was at question '77 [F64]' (6.4 What do the inclusive measures of these strategies/policies/policy initiatives focus on? Tick all that apply:)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '80 [F642]' (6.4.2 Do any of the criteria for research assessment address gender inequality or other grounds of discrimination (across disciplines, research types, career stages, research roles, peer review, training and mentoring, other...)?)

Please write your answer here:

6.5 Given that you have indicated different grounds of inequality covered in your policy, what are the terms most frequently used in your policies and initiatives on inclusive research careers?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Non-discrimination
- Intersectionality
- Representation
- Gender+ equality
- Diversity
- Inclusiveness/inclusion
- Inclusive equality
- Equity/equality
- None of the above
- Other:

Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation). Please comment/explain especially if multiple terms are used (non-mandatory)

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please write your answer here:

Or upload the document, specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation, e.g., machine translation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '71 [F622]' (6.2.2 Do these strategies/policies/policy instruments also include intersections of gender equality with other grounds of inequality and power relations?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

6.6 Is there any kind of evaluation process on already adopted / implemented policies / initiatives?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '65 [F62]' (6.2 Do these national strategies/policies/policy instruments promote gender equality?

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Yes' at question '68 [F621]' (6.2.1 If no, is the topic of inclusive research careers addressed in more broadly conceived national policies or strategies for the higher education and research institutions (e.g., strategic plans, national research and innovation policies etc.)?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, what are the key factors for the success in implementation? Please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '85 [F66]' (6.6 Is there any kind of evaluation process on already adopted / implemented policies / initiatives?)

Please write your answer here:

6.7 Is there a difference in the social security coverage in your country between different types of researcher positions (permanent or temporary) and PhD students on fellowships, in the following situations?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

6.7.1 If yes, tick all that apply:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '87 [F67]' (6.7 Is there a difference in the social security coverage in your country between different types of researcher positions (permanent or temporary) and PhD students on fellowships, in the following situations?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Illness
- Unemployment
- Work-life Balance
- Maternity and parental leave / support (e.g., length and allowance during the leave, ...) and post maternity /parental leave support while back to work
- Retirement
- Other:

6.7.2 Please explain shortly the differences in coverage in each selected situation:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '87 [F67]' (6.7 Is there a difference in the social security coverage in your country between different types of researcher positions (permanent or temporary) and PhD students on fellowships, in the following situations?)

Please write your answer here:

6.7.3 Please identify in which of the above situations ticked in 6.7, gender discrimination, direct or indirect, is more likely to occur and what are the conditions (different conditions in the coverage by social security, work-life balance in Fellowship Holder Statutes versus General Labour Code, etc.).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '87 [F67]' (6.7 Is there a difference in the social security coverage in your country between different types of researcher positions (permanent or temporary) and PhD students on fellowships, in the following situations?)

Please write your answer here:

6.8 Are there other debates ongoing at the national level for more inclusive Social Security coverage?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '91 [F68]' (6.8 Are there other debates ongoing at the national level for more inclusive Social Security coverage?)

Please write your answer here:

6.9 Has your ministry or any other relevant national/regional authority faced any of the following obstacles in developing policies/policy initiatives and actions on gender-inclusive research careers?

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Uncertainty about the terminology to be used
- Lack of a unified understanding of the underlying concepts
- Prevalent masculine notions about the research profession (total dedication, extreme focus on performance etc.)
- Not yet on the national agenda
- Still under preliminary debate
- Lack of political /societal awareness
- Lack of Gender Equality Structures
- Budgetary constraints
- Lack of gender disaggregated data

- None of the above
- Other:

6.10 What initiatives are needed to raise the issue of inclusive research careers on the national and European agenda?

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Mutual learning initiatives
- Clear guidelines from the European Commission (EC)
- Advanced legal framework at national level
- Financial incentives and support
- Other:

6.11 Based on your experience, what recommendations could you provide at the national level to promote the design and implementation of gender inclusive research careers?

Please write your answer here:

6.12 Please share case studies or good practices that have helped your country in strengthening inclusive research careers.

Please write your answer here:

7. Gender-Based Violence

Instruction: Please read your country reports from the UniSAFE project available on [the Zenodo community](#) (please use the search box at the top of the page to search for your country's national report) and indicate any new developments since 1 May 2021. Please note that the UniSAFE project covers EU-27 and among the Associated Countries Iceland, UK, Serbia and Turkey.

Gender-Based Violence (GBV) is defined as all forms of gendered violations and abuse, including but not limited to, physical violence, psychological violence, economic and financial violence, sexual violence, sexual harassment, gender harassment, stalking, organisational violence and harassment. GBV can occur in both online and offline contexts, and also includes emerging forms of violence, experienced as violence, violations and abuse not yet necessarily named or recognised as violence.

Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) are defined as any public or private body financing research and innovation.

7.1. Have national policies been adopted to address GBV in RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan). These policies may target applicants for funding and the entire funding process, as well as the internal organisation of the RFO itself.

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '97 [G71]' (7.1. Have national policies been adopted to address GBV in RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan). These policies may target applicants for funding and the entire funding process, as well as the internal organisation of the RFO itself.)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '98 [G611]' (If yes, does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not available online please upload the document and highlight the relevant text. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '98 [G611]' (If yes, does the policy address GBV on other grounds than gender (taken an intersectional perspective)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

If it is planned, please name the policy and any possible details already known.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '97 [G71]' (7.1. Have national policies been adopted to address GBV in RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan). These policies may target applicants for funding and the entire funding process, as well as the internal organisation of the RFO itself.)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why not.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '97 [G71]' (7.1. Have national policies been adopted to address GBV in RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan). These policies may target

applicants for funding and the entire funding process, as well as the internal organisation of the RFO itself.)

Please write your answer here:

7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- It is planned
- No, and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '103 [G72]' (7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not available online, please upload the document and highlight the relevant text. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '103 [G72]' (7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

If it is planned, please name the policy and any possible details already known.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'It is planned' at question '103 [G72]' (7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why not.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No, and it is not planned' at question '103 [G72]' (7.2 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RFOs? (e.g., a declaration, a strategy, an action plan)?)

Please write your answer here:

7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?

Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No but it is planned
- No and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please provide a link, specify the relevant passages (and if not in English provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '108 [G73]' (7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

Or if not available online, please upload the document and highlight the relevant text. Please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '108 [G73]' (7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

If it is planned, please name the policy and any possible details already known.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No but it is planned' at question '108 [G73]' (7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

If no, please provide an explanation for why not.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No and it is not planned' at question '108 [G73]' (7.3 Have national policies to address GBV in RPOs been adopted which include measures or actions to be taken by RPOs themselves? (e.g., an institutional policy, procedure etc.)?)

Please write your answer here:

8. Gender dimension in research, teaching and innovation

This section focuses specifically on national initiatives – and regional where relevant – to promote the integration of the gender dimension in the content of research and innovation projects (i.e., sex/gender analysis in R&I). Note that these questions are not about gender balance in R&I teams. We encourage you to check our [glossary](#) for clarification of the concepts related to this section.

8.1 What kind of actions have been taken by your national authority at national level to promote the integration of the gender dimension into R&I?

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Financial incentives/support to promote the gender dimension in research and innovation
- Financial incentives/support to promote the gender dimension in teaching content
- A specific funding programme on gender studies is in place
- Requiring applicants to specify whether they are considering sex and/or gender in their research/ innovation proposal
- Inclusion of gender experts in the research teams is encouraged in the R&I calls
- Training on sex/gender analysis for the research team is considered as an eligible cost in national funding schemes
- Established processes to evaluate the integration of the sex/gender analysis into R&I (i.e., as part of the institution's mandate and through well-established guidelines on the evaluation)
- Positive action measures to favour projects that integrate sex and/or gender (go to the glossary for a definition of positive action measures)
- Guidelines on the gender dimension of R&I for applicants
- Guidelines on the gender dimension of R&I for evaluators
- Training on the gender dimension of R&I for applicants
- Training on the gender dimension of R&I for evaluators
- Experts on gender in R&I are included in the evaluation committees
- Communication campaign to make visible the support to sex/gender analysis
- Dissemination materials on the gender dimension in R&I available (videos, academic papers, leaflets...)
- Actions to promote sex/gender analysis in university-level curricula
- None of the above
- Other:

8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

8.2.1 If no, does your national authority plan to make a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Please explain the context of the plans:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '115 [H821]' (8.2.1 If no, does your national authority plan to make a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

8.3 What kind of strategy or policy has your national authority adopted?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- National law
- Specific strategy, policy and/or measure (e.g., gender equality plan)
- Other:

Please provide the name of your national/regional official policy related to the information requested above, link(s) to supporting documents you consider relevant for the analysis and specify the relevant passages (if not in English, provide a translation, e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

If not publicly available online, please upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages, and if not in English provide a translation (e.g. machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

8.4 What are the main goals of your strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)
Please write your answer here:

8.5 Does your national/regional strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I include an intersectional approach?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

8.5.1 If yes, tick off for which inequality grounds:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '121 [H85]' (8.5 Does your national/regional strategy or policy on the gender dimension in R&I include an intersectional approach?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Inequality grounds in line with antidiscrimination directive (taken together)
- Ethnicity
- Socio-economic status
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

8.6 Does your national/regional strategy or policy include the innovation and private sectors in the objective of producing non-biased knowledge and solutions for society as a whole?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

8.7 How is the strategy/policy on the gender dimension in R&I implemented? Please provide information on the unit(s) responsible for implementing the policy, the actions taken so far, and

the structures developed for its implementation, including technical, human and economic resources.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

8.8 How is the policy/strategy on the gender dimension in R&I monitored? Please provide information on the actions and structures, if any, established to supervise the concrete actions developed by this national authority/other agents of the R&I system, the indicators used and their outcomes.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

8.9 Has the policy/strategy on the gender dimension in R&I been evaluated? *

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, what impact/outcome has your policy on the gender dimension in R&I made?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '126 [H89]' (8.9 Has the policy/strategy on the gender dimension in R&I been evaluated?)

Please write your answer here:

8.10 Please explain the challenges/obstacles, if any, the national authority/ies has/have faced in implementing this policy/strategy on the gender dimension in R&I:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Please write your answer here:

8.11 If relevant, do regional RFOs in your country require the integration of the gender dimension in R&I projects?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '114 [H82]' (8.2 Does your national authority have a strategy or policy aimed at integrating sex/gender analysis into R&I content?)

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No
- Not applicable

8.12 Does your national authority have a policy or strategy aimed at promoting sex/gender analysis in university-level curricula?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '130 [H12]' (8.12 Does your national authority have a policy or strategy aimed at promoting sex/gender analysis in university-level curricula?)

Please write your answer here:

Or upload the document(s), specify the relevant passages and provide an English translation (e.g., machine translation).

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '130 [H12]' (8.12 Does your national authority have a policy or strategy aimed at promoting sex/gender analysis in university-level curricula?)

Please upload at most 5 files

Kindly attach the aforementioned documents along with the survey

8.13 What would your national authority need to advance some of the measures mentioned above or others to promote the gender dimension in the R&I content?

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Financial resources
- More awareness on the relevance on sex/gender analysis for R&I
- Exchange experiences on how to consider the gender dimension in R&I from an intersectional perspective
- Capacity-building
- Training materials
- Mandatory policies (e.g., conditional funding)
- I don't know
- Other:

9. GEP monitoring / Evaluating GEP impact

9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education? *

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

9.2 If yes, is it mandated by:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- The law
- A policy
- Both
- Other

9.3 To which organisations does the GEP requirement apply?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Public HEIs
- Private HEIs
- Public RPOs
- Private RPOs
- Public administration bodies
- Private R&I sector companies with a certain number of employees
- Other:

9.4 Does the GEP requirement include intersections with other discriminatory grounds?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please tick all that apply:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?) *and* Answer was 'Yes' at question '137 [J94]' (9.4 Does the GEP requirement include intersections with other discriminatory grounds?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Ethnicity,
- Socio-economic background/class
- Age
- Disability
- Sexual orientation
- Gender identity
- LGBTQIA+
- Religion
- Other:

9.5 Is the GEP requirement envisioned to contribute to the development of Inclusive Research Careers?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '139 [J95]' (9.5 Is the GEP requirement envisioned to contribute to the development of Inclusive Research Careers?)

Please write your answer here:

9.6 Does the national GEP requirement fulfil the following EU GEP mandatory building blocks?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please tick all that are required:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '141 [J960]' (9.6 Does the national GEP requirement fulfil the following EU GEP mandatory building blocks?)

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Publication: a formal document published on the institution's website and signed by the top management
- Dedicated resources: commitment of resources and expertise in gender equality to implement the plan
- Data collection and monitoring: sex/gender disaggregated data on personnel (and students, for the establishments concerned) and annual reporting based on indicators
- Training: awareness raising/training on gender equality and unconscious gender biases for staff and decision-makers

Please provide additional information here regarding the mandatory elements:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '134 [J91]' (9.1 Is a Gender Equality Plan required at the national/regional level in your country in research and innovation or higher education?)

Please write your answer here:

9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please briefly describe the following aspects:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

9.8 Are indicators defined for national/regional GEP monitoring by the responsible authority?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please specify these indicators:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '146 [J98]' (9.8 Are indicators defined for national/regional GEP monitoring by the responsible authority?)

Please write your answer here:

9.9 Is the monitoring of GEPs part of the national/ regional monitoring system/ policy only, or is it related to ERA monitoring activities?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- ERA policy
- National/ regional policy
- Both
- Other

9.10 Does a publicly available database of GEPs exist at the national/regional level?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

If yes, please provide the link:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '149 [J910]' (9.10 Does a publicly available database of GEPs exist at the national/regional level?)

Please write your answer here:

9.11 Does this system measure impact in terms of the defined gender equality priorities (at national or international level)?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

9.12 Which features of GEPs does the system monitor?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '144 [J97]' (9.7 Does a national/regional system exist for GEP monitoring?)

Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- GEP is a publicly available document
- Dedicated resources are allocated for gender equality work
- System for collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data is in place
- Training and capacity building are planned
- Reporting on gender balance in leadership and decision-making
- Monitoring of gender equality in recruitment and promotion processes at the institutional level
- Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content
- Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment are in place
- None of the above
- Other:

9.13 What impact on gender equality in your country have the following features of GEPs had (where 1= no impact, 5 = strong impact)?

Please choose the appropriate response for each item:

	1	2	3	4	5
GEP is a publicly available document					
Dedicated resources are allocated for gender equality work					
System for collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data is in place					
Training and capacity building are planned					
Reporting on gender balance in leadership and decision-making					
Monitoring of gender equality in recruitment and promotion processes at the institutional level					
Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content					
Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment are in place					
Other, please specify					

9.14 Does a national evaluation system exist for GEP implementation?

Choose one of the following answers
Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- It is planned
- No, and it is not planned
- I don't know

If yes, please describe its main principles and the periodicity of the GEP implementation evaluation.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '154 [J914]' (9.14 Does a national evaluation system exist for GEP implementation?)

Please write your answer here:

10. Relevant stakeholders and organisations

Note: the stakeholder organisations need not focus only on gender equality but could be concerned with other relevant issues (race/ethnicity, LGBTQI+ rights, international mobility, PhD associations, early-career researcher associations, precarity, position of returning researchers after international mobility etc.)

10.1 Which national stakeholders active in the field of research, higher education and/or innovation (NGOs, citizens/students/researchers/other associations) would be suitable for cooperation with GENDERACTIONplus in relation to citizen and stakeholder engagement? Please, provide the requested information below.

10.2 Please add any other comments, ideas or tips on public/citizen engagement:

Please write your answer here:

11. Final remarks

If there are aspects that this survey has not covered and you would like to share them, please add any comments here:

Please write your answer here:

Submit your survey.

Your response has been recorded. Thank you very much for your time!

GET IN TOUCH WITH US!

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